

NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON FAMILY PLANNING (NCFP)

Family Planning: Reaching the Unreached

Kathmandu, Nepal
18 - 19 March 2019

(४-५ चैत्र २०७५)

ABSTRACT BOOK

**NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
FAMILY PLANNING (NCFP)**
Family Planning: Reaching the Unreached
Kathmandu, Nepal
18-19 March 2019

Abstracts

DISCLAIMER

The responsibility for opinions expressed, in articles, studies and other contributions in this publication rests solely with their authors, and this publication does not constitute an endorsement by the NCFP 2019 of the opinions so expressed in them.

Official website of the conference: www.ncfpnepal.org

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Edited by **Ashmin Hari Bhattarai**

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THEME

Family Planning: Reaching the Unreached

Sub-themes

- Met and unmet need of FP services
- Reaching the unreached population for FP services
- Demand generation and behavior change
- Expanding access to quality FP services
- Systems strengthening for FP services

Objectives of the Conference

- To bring together health professionals and community voice involved in Adolescent Sexual and Reproductive Health/Family Planning (ASRH/FP).
- To bolster the network and share knowledge.
- To disseminate new knowledge and information about RH/FP.
- To integrate new knowledge and research concepts into current and future improved practice and research.
- To prepare extended action plan incorporating recommendations of conference.

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Ref. No.

Welcome from the Chair

Dear Friends,

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, I am delighted to welcome you to the National Conference on Family Planning (NCFP) in Kathmandu, Nepal. This conference is the result of six months of rigorous planning, meetings, reflection, decision-making and finally, here we are! I am confident that NCFP 2019 will demonstrate how, in so many ways, we are progressing in family planning service.

The theme for NCFP 2019 is "Family Planning: Reaching the Unreached" which aspires to provide a very important platform to improve the quality and reach of family planning services among adolescents, postpartum and post-abortion women, poor and marginalized population and migrants.

This conference will host number of executive sessions led by technical influencers in family Planning and I earnestly encourage you to take this opportunity to participate and share your invaluable insights and knowledge. As I am sure this conference will instill you with unlimited benefits and would open new frontiers for the current family planning challenges in the varied landscape of Nepalese healthcare, we continue to shape the national family planning service in terms of research, education and clinical practice. This conference is our opportunity to share and celebrate our work, to greet old friends and make new, but ultimately to remember that our time together in Kathmandu demonstrates that, in many ways, we share one goal: to improve the quality and reach of family planning services. And we should never forget that we do that well.

There are many people to thank. The Scientific Sub-committee ably led by Dr. Laxmi Raj Pathak as Chair. The members of the Organizing Committee, Logistics Management Sub-committee, and Communication and Media Sub-committee without whom this Conference would not have been possible. Thank you all for your leadership, vision and contribution in bringing this Conference to us. And of course, thanks to the partner organizations and supporters for their contribution, technical and financial to make this Conference happen.

I wish you a wonderful Conference to exchange thoughts and ideas that will generate remarkable initiatives and contribute in enhancing access to family planning services.

Dr. R.P. Bichha
Chair

National Conference on Family Planning

Word of Welcome from the Scientific Sub-Committee

Dear Colleagues & Friends,

Greetings!

As the chair of the scientific sub-committee, it gives me immense pleasure to welcome all the eminent personalities to National Conference on Family Planning (NCFP) 2019 in Kathmandu.

Throughout the world, family planning is growing in strategic importance not only to healthcare delivery but also to the development. However, the development of quality driven service and systems to meet the increasing need for equitable and accessible family planning service to clients with unmet needs remains a challenge. Therefore, the theme chosen for this conference is “Family Planning: Reaching the Unreached”.

NCFP 2019 is a common platform where we will share our remarkable research work, programmatic interventions and experiences on family planning. We look forward to a better transition of evolving evidence into practice, building quality driven service and systems that avails equitable and accessible family planning service to all, especially the “unreached”.

The Conference is structured along five subthemes and composed of plenary and parallel sessions that bring an equity lens to the overall context and crucial sectors for family planning. In a short period of time, response has been overwhelming. We received a total of 78 abstracts of which 24 have been selected for oral presentations at 6 parallel sessions and 30 are confirmed as poster presentations.

As the first national conference on family planning, this will become an ideal forum and right time for the exchange of new information, the discussion of research results, and the progress we made to the commitments of FP2020. Additionally, attending the Conference also provides a unique opportunity to network and meet with colleagues, healthcare professionals, researchers and program implementors in family planning from across the nation to exchange knowledge and to share experiences.

It is our hope that this Conference can contribute to a rethinking of policies and practices to ensure that national responses bring about justice in family planning, reaching the unreached.

Have a great conference time!

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'L. Pathak', written in a cursive style.

Dr. Laxmi Raj Pathak
Chair
Scientific Sub-Committee

CONFERENCE & OVERVIEW & PROGRAM FEATURES

DATES AND VENUE OF CONFERENCE

- Hotel Yak & Yeti, Kathmandu.
- 18-19 March 2019

PROGRAM FEATURES

- **Plenary Sessions:** Well-known and distinguished speakers from government, development partners, and private sectors will present on critical issues on family planning during the plenary sessions. These sessions serve as special platform where broad-ranging debate maybe conducted to produce major statements and recommendations.
- **Parallel Sessions:** oral abstract presentations on the five sub-themes are the main attraction of the conference. Four different speakers are allowed 10-minute presentations each, followed by discussions. The chair of each session facilitates the session and encourages the participants to ask questions.
- **Poster Exhibition:** Poster exhibition comprises of abstracts presented in poster form. Presenters will be assigned scheduled times to discuss their posters during the conference. The posters will be exhibited in scheduled locations within the conference venue.
- **Exhibition stalls:** Innovative stalls will be designed within the conference venue which provides opportunity for partners to showcase their works in family planning. These are spaces where participants and organizations come across each other for their marketing and branding.

08:00-09:00	Registration – Lobby	
09:00-11:20	Opening Ceremonies – Hall 1	
	<p>Inaugural session (Chair person, Chief guest, Distinguished guests)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome Remarks FP Situation in Nepal – Dr. R.P. Bichha, Director, Family Welfare Division Family Planning is a human right – UNFPA Country Representative, Lubna Baqi Remarks 	
11:20-11:45	Refreshment Break & Photo session	
11:45-12:45	Parallel Session 1 - Hall 1	Parallel Session 2 - Hall 2
	<p>Met and unmet need of FP Services Chair: Dr. Ram Sharan Pathak, CDPS, TU Co-chair: Dr. Binjwala Shrestha, IOM Presenters: Jiblal Pokharel Awareness and use of D'zire condom among urban Nepalese men Saugat Joshi Reasons for discontinuation of use and expulsion of immediate post-partum intrauterine device in Nepal Santosh Paudel Unmet need of family planning in a rural district Syangja, Nepal Navaraj Bhattarai Factors affecting the post abortion contraceptive uptake: An analysis of Ipas Nepal supported health facilities in Nepal</p>	<p>Reaching the unreached population for FP services - A Chair: Dr. Laxmi Raj Pathak Co-chair: Dr. Neeta Shrestha, UNFPA Presenters: Sangita Khatri Roving Auxiliary Nurses-Midwives (RANMs): A community-based approach to delivering reproductive health services to hard-to-reach (HTR) populations in Nepal Rajendra Gurung Can "skilled service provider visits" expand availability and uptake of Long Acting Reversible Contraceptive (LARC) services in rural Nepal? Tina Gurung A Visiting Service Provider with dedication and passion to reach the unreached Jeeban Ghimire Early Marriage, Family Planning Status and Child Nutrition in a Dis-advantaged Chepang Community of Dhading, Nepal</p>
12:45-14:15	Lunch Break & Poster Exhibition	
14:15-15:30	Plenary Session 1 – Hall 1	
	<p>Stagnant mCPR: Exploring the reasons and way forward Presenter: Dr. Prakash Dev Pant, MITRA Samaj Moderator: Sabitri Sapkota, Nyaya Health Nepal Panelists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. R.P. Bichha, Director, Family Welfare Division • Mr. K.P. Bista, DG, FPAN • Dr. Y.B. Karki • Ms. Latika Maskey Pradhan, UNFPA 	

15:30-16:00	Refreshment Break & Photo session	
16:00-17:00	Parallel Session 3- Hall 1	Parallel Session 4- Hall 2
	<p>Reaching the unreached population for FP services - B</p> <p>Chair: Dr. Bal Krishna Subedi Co-chair: Sagar Dahal, Sr. PHA, MOSD, Province 1</p> <p>Presenters:</p> <p>Reena Lama Women 4 women - Improving Sexual and Reproductive Health of Female Sex Workers in Nepal</p> <p>Kamala Devi Lamichhane Use of contraceptive methods among young married women in Nepal</p> <p>Tripti Dhakal Barriers and facilitators to use of family planning services among adolescents in Arghakhanchi: qualitative findings</p> <p>Sujit Kumar Sah Contraceptive Choices and Determinants of Low Uptake of Long Acting Reversible Contraceptives by Young People (15-24 Years) in Nepal</p>	<p>Demand generation and behavior change</p> <p>Chair: Mahendra Prasad Shrestha, Chief, HCD, MoHP</p> <p>Co-chair: Netra Prasad Bhatta, Sr. Program Specialist-FP/RH, USAID</p> <p>Presenters:</p> <p>Naramaya Subba Limbu Integration of the Standard Days Method (Malachakra), a fertility awareness method, for women in marginalized communities of Rupandehi</p> <p>Rajan Parajuli Using Entertainment-Education to motivate FP Use</p> <p>Reena Bhagat Awareness and Practice of Family Planning Services among Married Women of Reproductive Age in a Rural Municipality of Saptari District, Nepal</p> <p>Sanjeev Kumar Sahani A formative Research on understanding the situation and identifying needs, preference and enabling and impeding behaviors in among poor and marginalized women 9 districts of Nepal</p>

Theme: Family Planning: Reaching the Unreached

Chair and Chief Guest	Topics	Presenters
Chair: Dr. R.P. Bichha, Chair, Organizing Committee, NCFP 2019 Chief guest: Hon'able Minister, Mr. Upendra Yadav, Ministry of Health & Population	FP Situation in Nepal	Dr. R.P. Bichha, Director, Family Welfare Division
	Reaching FP2020 targets: Challenges and opportunities	Lubna Baqi, Country Representative, UNFPA Nepal

Biography

Dr. Ram Padarath Bichha is the Director for Family Welfare Division under Department of Health Services, Ministry of Health and Population, Nepal. He is renowned in the country for his specialization in Paediatrics & Neonatology. Dr. Bichha has experiences of leading various public health division under Department of Health Services.

Lubna Baqi is the Representative of United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) for Nepal since 3 October 2017. She has over 25 years of experience working in the development field, many of them at the United Nations Population Fund, UNFPA.

Since 2011, Baqi has served as Deputy Regional Director, UNFPA APRO, providing oversight and support to the 23 UNFPA country offices in the region and managing the work of the programme, technical and communications teams in the regional office including regional interventions and strategic partnerships. Prior to this, she was the

Associate Director, UN Development Operations Coordination Office in New York (2007-2010), where she led the Programme Support and Global Quality Standards Team, responsible for promoting programme coherence and innovation under the UN development system.

Earlier, she was UNFPA Representative in Sri Lanka and Country Director in the Maldives (2003-2007), supporting the development and implementation of programme operations as well as the humanitarian response to the devastating 2004 Asian Tsunami. She also served in Egypt as the acting UNFPA Representative and Deputy Representative (2001-2003).

Baqi is a British national and she holds a Master of Science degree in Economics from the Development Planning Unit, University College London, London University, and a Bachelor of Arts in Social Sciences from the University of Westminster, UK.

PARALLEL SESSION 1

Sub-theme : Met and unmet need of FP services
Chair : Dr. Ram Sharan Pathak, CDPS, TU
Co-chair : Dr. Binjwala Shrestha, Institute of Medicine

11:45

Hall 1

Awareness and use of D'zire condom among urban Nepalese men

Jiblal Pokharel¹, Jeffrey Barnes²

¹Nepal CRS Company, ²Shops Plus

Abstract

This study reports on the results of a targeted condom social marketing campaign on awareness and use of condoms among urban men. The study was a pre and post campaign survey of urban men to create an evidence-based approach for media selection in promoting its product among its users and enabled CRS to show a significant impact of a mass media campaign in increasing awareness and demand for the brand.

Nepal CRS Company ran a marketing campaign for its premier D'zire condom in September and October 2018 in numerous media outlets targeted at urban men of 18-49 age group. Extensive marketing campaign through TV channels, radio channels, internet sites, newspapers, digital display boards at the airports as well as flanges in shops was conducted in urban areas throughout Nepal. Pre and Post campaign survey was conducted to evaluate the condom brand preference and perception, sexual behavior and condom use, media habits, campaign recall and changes in awareness and use.

The awareness and ever-use and campaign recall of D'zire condoms increased significantly among the target group. The ever-use of D'zire condoms increased 100% among the core target group with a significant increase in the perception of quality and packing of D'zire condoms.

The campaign was a "High Impact Campaign" valuable for increasing the brand awareness and ever-use of condoms among core target group and evaluating the cost effectiveness of each media channel. The media habits and purchasing behavior have highlighted the need to destigmatize the condom purchase as well as the need for gender transformative messaging destigmatizing the condom purchase.

11:55

Hall 1

Reasons for discontinuation of use and expulsion of immediate post-partum intrauterine device in Nepal

Saugat Joshi¹, Mahesh Puri¹, Yasaswi Dhungel¹, Iqbal Shah², Erin Pearson³,
Elina Pradhan⁴, Aayush Khadka²

¹Center for Research on Environment, Health and Population Activities (CREHPA),
Nepal, ²The Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health, United States,
³Ipas, United States, ⁴The World Bank Group, United States

Abstract

Background: The immediate postpartum intrauterine device (PPIUD) is a safe, convenient, and cost-effective method of contraception for Nepali women. However, despite its many advantages, PPIUD use remains low and little is known about women's perceptions of and experience with the device. This study investigates reasons for continuation, discontinuation, and expulsion of PPIUD as reported by Nepali women.

Methods: In-depth interviews were conducted with 36 women who had PPIUDs inserted immediately after delivery in six tertiary hospitals in Nepal. At the time of interview, 12 women were continuing to use PPIUDs, 13 women had discontinued using PPIUDs, and 11 women had experienced PPIUD expulsion. Interviews were audio recorded, transcribed, translated into English from Nepali, and analyzed using a thematic approach within the grounded theory framework.

Results: Commonly cited reasons for PPIUD discontinuation included familial pressure to discontinue, experience of side effects, incorrect insertion of the device, and poor quality of family planning counselling. Women who experienced PPIUD expulsion were more likely to discontinue use and have negative perceptions of the device. Women who were continuing PPIUD use were more likely to be educated, have a supportive family environment, have experienced fewer complications, and have received higher quality family planning counselling both before and after insertion.

Conclusion: Provision of high quality and timely family planning counselling directed at both women and their family members may reduce PPIUD discontinuation. Improving provider insertion skills could contribute to lower rates of PPIUD expulsion and discontinuation as well.

Unmet need of family planning in a rural district Syangja, Nepal

Santosh Paudel¹, Suwat Srisorrachatr²

¹Health Office, Kaski, Nepal, ²Mahidol University, Thailand

Abstract

The unmet need of family planning can explain as the gap in between individual contraceptives behavior and their fertility preference. This study aims to find out the determinants of unmet need of family planning and explore the associations of unmet need with predisposing, reinforcing and enabling factors. except this researcher trying to identify the different situation regarding unmet need in the context of the study area (rural setting of Nepal). This cross-sectional study was carried out in Syangja district among MWRA. A total of 295 women were selected with clustered random sampling technique. Descriptive statistic along with chi-square test was applied to compute the association between variables. A set of structured questionnaires were designed to collect the data. The data was collected from Jan. 19th to Feb. 14th, 2014 in eight VDCs of the district.

The result of this study mostly focused on the unmet need which was analyzed in two different ways, on the basis of WHO definition of unmet need and analysis on the basis of contextual approach. According to the WHO definition, 11 percent unmet needs were found whereas unmet need on the basis of contextual study was 54 percent. With a big controversy, the current users were 61.2 percent in the district. Mostly, this is because of improper choice of family planning method and early marries. About 80% had history of early marriage (before 20 years). mean age of marriage was 19 ± 2.4 years.

Despite of good knowledge and strong social support the status of unmet need was quite high because of knowledge of husband and low attitude toward family planning. Similarly, dependency of MWRA on decision making with husband most of who were out of country. Thus, research concluded that husband knowledge and attitude regarding family planning should improve and health literacy and general literacy is two different aspect of awareness in the community.

12:15

Hall 1

Factors affecting the post abortion contraceptive uptake: An analysis of Ipas Nepal supported health facilities in Nepal

Navaraj Bhattarai¹, Mukta Shah¹, Sunita Poudel¹, Dr. Shibesh Chandra Regmi¹
¹Ipas Nepal

Abstract

Background: Post abortion family contraceptive is important to avert the subsequent unintended pregnancy following induced or post abortion service. This paper assesses the attributes of post abortion contraceptive uptake.

Methodology: This is an analysis of 21,661 deidentified individual records of women who received abortion services from July 2017 to June 2018 at 257 Ipas supported public and private health facilities. Descriptive statistics were reported using frequencies and percentage. All unadjusted and adjusted analyses were done in Stata 14 using logistic regressions clustering on facilities.

Result: Overall, 86% women received contraceptives and 18% received LARC following abortion services. In the adjusted model, second trimester abortion clients were less likely to receive PAFP (OR=0.57,95% CI:0.41-0.79) compared to first trimester clients. Strong dose-response relationship was observed between LARC use and number of living children. Clients using medical abortion were less likely to use LARC (OR:0.69, 95%CI: 0.54-0.88) compared to those who used surgical method. Likewise, compared to the clients who received induced abortion service, clients using post abortion care were less likely to use LARC (OR: 0.38, 95%CI: 0.23-0.63) . Clients who received abortion service from Ipas trained providers were 2.2 times more likely to use LARC compared to those who were not Ipas trained.

Recommendation: The finding suggest that the focus should be on the clients who received second trimester abortion services, clients who used medical abortion services, clients who used abortion post abortion care along with providers quality training and post training support to improve PAFP uptake and improve method mix.

Sub-theme : Reaching the unreached population
for FP services-A
Chair : Dr. Laxmi Raj Pathak
Co-chair : Dr. Neeta Shrestha, UNFPA

11:45

Hall 2

Roving Auxiliary Nurses–Midwives (RANMs): A community–based approach to delivering reproductive health services to hard-to-reach (HTR) populations in Nepal

Sangita Khatri¹, Marcie Rubardt², Naramaya Limbu³

¹Save the Children, Nepal, ²Save the Children, United States,

³Institute for Reproductive Health

Abstract

Background: Existing family planning (FP) strategies have not successfully met the high unmet need among HTR communities in Nepal. As a result, the Ministry of Health proposed testing a more qualified community-level provider: the RANM, to bridge the geographic and cultural gaps these groups experience.

Methodology: With leadership from Rupandehi District Public Health Office and the FACT project, HTR areas were identified based on consultative meetings and formative research. A plan was developed to deploy 9 RANMs in 6 rural Village Development Communities and 2 municipalities for 12 months. RANMs and stakeholders then identified priority “clusters” where HTR groups were concentrated. A pre-post sample of 424 women participated in a community survey, focus group discussion and in-depth interviews to assess the RANM intervention.

Results: 81% of primary RANM contacts were from HTR groups (Muslim, Madeshi and Dalit ethnicities). Among home visits conducted, 62% included contact with the spouse or in-laws of the primary client. 24% of primary contacts included direct service provision, 30% were pregnancy-related care and 20% were FP services.

Lessons learned: The RANM model reaches groups who may be otherwise unreached with FP services. Using other MNH services such as antenatal and postnatal services as an entry point may offer an opportunity to build trust, subsequently allowing consideration of FP where low FP use may be associated with social and cultural barriers. Finally, by offering sensitive services at the household level, RANMs also reach women who may otherwise not access services.

11:55

Hall 2

Can “skilled service provider visits” expand availability and uptake of Long Acting Reversible Contraceptive (LARC) services in rural Nepal?

Dr. Rajendra Gurung¹, Maureen Dariang²

¹NHSSP Nepal, ²NHSSP Myanmar

Abstract

Nepal’s CPR for modern FP methods has remained stagnant a, unmet need for contraceptives is high, and uptake of LARCs which include implants and IUCDs is sub-optimal. Human resource shortfalls in health mean that innovative methods have been tried for LARC expansion particularly to increase access to underutilized methods in underserved populations.

Since the successful piloting of VSP, an innovative model of LARCs service delivery in Ramechhap (2015/16) the GoN, through D(P)HOs (2016/17), palikas (2017/18) and provinces (2018/19) has worked to improve access and uptake of LARCs, by mobilizing VSPs. LARC services are also provided by 2 private sector providers (ADRA and MSI) mobilizing VSPs in selected districts with outstanding outcomes. VSPs are professional ANMs or SNs who are deployed as dedicated mobile LARCs providers and are trained in IUCDs and implant insertions/removals, and are deputed to provide FP services especially in hard to reach areas. VSPs expand LARC services under 2 modalities: direct LARCs service provision by VSPs in health facilities where there was no LARCs services and on-site coaching and mentoring of trained health service providers at remote facilities who are unable to provide LARCs services due to low skill retention and confidence.

This presentation based on KIs and secondary data analysis explores the progress that has been achieved in terms of improving LARC services through the VSP implementation models and the lessons learnt to inform its future course so that larger goals of sustainable and cost-effective FP provision are met in the immediate and long-term.

12:05

Hall 2

A Visiting Service Provider with dedication and passion to reach the unreached

Tina Gurung¹, Laxmi Ghimire¹, Ashmin Hari Bhattarai¹

¹ADRA Nepal

Abstract

Twenty-six years old lady and just married, Laxmi Ghimire from Chapakot Municipality, Syangja has been working as Visiting Service Provider (VSP) to reach the unreached of Rupandehi district since August 2018. She stays away from her home and recently married husband with spirit to help people with unmet need of FP access FP services in the district. She travels in Devdaha Municipality and Gaidahawa and Rohini Rural Municipality to educate people with low level of FP awareness and provide FP service to them. After completion of her ANM degree she has been working in rural communities to serve hard to reach and marginalized communities. **"I enjoy working as VSP and serving people for their unmet need"** Said Laxmi.

People of her working zone generally start think about FP method after having 5-6 children. Even they do not have any information about the service center where they get the service. From August to December 2018, she counselled 160 women and provided LARC service to 146 women (144 implant and 2 IUCD). **"She made me understand how family planning helps me have planned number of children and keep enough spacing between two children...."** Tribun Nisa, Client

She has been providing service to people focusing on Muslim, Dalit and Madhesi populations. Muslims do not use family planning method because of their religious beliefs. When Laxmi went to the district and started talking regarding Fertility Awareness and Family Planning to Muslim people, they shouted her saying that, she is against their religion and they shut their door when they listen her voice. She did not give up and kept on visiting individuals and groups in that community. Father in Law, mother in law and husband along with other family member involve in counselling and slowly they started to listen her. Now people have started internalizing her message. They have started visiting health facility to receive family planning counselling and service from her. It is remarkable achievement in that Muslim community where people never felt comfortable talking about family planning before.

"I really enjoy working as a VSP. My self-confidence has also increased because I interact with community people and inform them about family planning... As I do this, I have realized I am living for a reason, a reason to create impact on lives of the unreached."
Laxmi Ghimire, VSP.

Early Marriage, Family Planning Status and Child Nutrition in a Disadvantaged Chepang Community of Dhading, Nepal

Jeeban Ghimire
Population, Gender and Development, Pokhara University

Abstract

Background: Several studies in Nepal, the status of family planning is lower and higher child malnutrition remaining significant public health and development agendas. However, there are limited studies conducted among vulnerable disadvantaged Chepang in Nepal.
Objective: To assess the family planning and child nutrition among Chepangs.

Methods: Two months long (Jan-Feb 2017) census-based household survey was carried out and obtained the anthropometric measurements of under two children in two Rural Municipalities of Dhading district. The data analyzed in SPSS 20 and ENA software. An ethical approval was obtained from Pokhara University Research Center (PURC) and Institutional Review Committee (IRC).

Results: Among 1,336 Chepang women of reproductive age interviewed, the mean age of the mother is found 27 years (SD 6.727) and mean age at marriage is 17 years (SD 2.939) and mean age at the time of first child found 18.75 years. Only 10% of women are currently using the family planning method. Out of 1227 the prevalence of stunted children (6-59 months) in the study area is 66.6 percent (64.0 - 69.2 95% C.I.). About 48 percent (45.2 - 50.7 95% C.I.) children are found underweight and 20 percent (18.1 - 22.6 95% C.I.) are wasted.

Recommendation: Formative research and interventions to prevent early marriage, early pregnancy and child malnutrition are strongly recommended to reach the unreached. The municipality should design specific programming and financing on family planning and child nutrition among disadvantaged communities.

PLENARY SESSION 1

Stagnant mCPR: Exploring the reasons and way forward

🕒 14:15 - 15:30 📍 Hall 1

Moderator and Panelists	Topic	Presenter
<p>Moderator: Sabitri Sapkota</p> <p>Panelists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. R.P. Bichha, Director, Family Welfare Division • Mr. K.P. Bista, FPAN • Dr. Y.B. Karki • Ms. Latika Maskey Pradhan, UNFPA 	<p>Stagnant mCPR: Exploring the reasons and way forward</p>	<p>Dr. Prakash Dev Pant, MITRA Samaj</p>

Biography

Dr. Prakash Dev Pant is a Nepali national actively involved in population, health and social research for more than 30 years. Former Associate Professor at Central Department of Population Studies, Tribhuvan University, he has received his PhD in Demography from the Australian National University, Canberra Australia (1991-1994).

He has worked with several national and overseas institutions. As a technical advisor, he has worked with the Government of Nepal on population and reproductive health studies and several DHS. In addition, he served as a Monitoring and Evaluation Advisor at Family Health International, Research Director at Population Services International/Nepal among others. As a resource person, Dr. Pant has conducted various workshops/training to project managers, research scholars, university students and stakeholders on monitor and evaluation, survey data analysis and GIS.

Dr. Pant has worked as a social science researcher and faculty for about 25 years at Tribhuvan University, in Nepal. He has also worked as a consultant for various I/NGOs and international donor agencies in Nepal. Currently, he is associated with a national level NGO called MITRA Samaj as the Chairperson.

PARALLEL SESSION **3**

Sub-theme : Reaching the unreached population for FP services - B

Chair : Dr. Bal Krishna Subedi

Co-chair : Sagar Dahal, Sr. PHA, MOSD, Province 1

 Hall 1

Women 4 women – Improving sexual and reproductive health of female sex workers in Nepal

Reena Lama¹, Purna shova Maharjan¹, Sachhit Gurung¹

¹Friends Affected & Infected Together in Hand (FAITH) Nepal

Abstract

Background: Sex work offers girls and young women from poor and marginalized communities a decent income. However, social exclusion and criminalization of sex work has limited their access to social and health institutions. Current female sex workers (FSWs) specific programming limits its focus on HIV, STIs and doesn't address their broader SRH needs. The Community-based outreach approach has proven successful in HIV program. The project analyzes the effectiveness of Community-based outreach in improving SRH status of FSWs in Kathmandu and Lalitpur districts.

Methodology: A national oversight committee was formed with representatives from Government, multilateral, I/NGOs and beneficiaries. Questionnaires were developed, pre-tested and finalized. An easy to use mobile app was developed to collect real time data. 11 FSWs were trained as community-based outreach workers on SRHR. Seven were mobilized for eight months (till February 2019).

Results: Total 1006 FSWs in pre-testing and 876 in post-test were reached. Pre-test: 982 (97.6%) reported using contraception – condom (97.1%), Pills (7.0%), depo (13.4%), Copper T (2.1%), Implant (1.9%) and female sterilization (2.2%). 245 (24.4%) used both condoms and one other contraceptive. 77% reported consistent condom use. 483 (48%) reported using emergency contraceptive pills (ECP) in their life time while 341 (33.9%) used ECP ranging from 1 to 12 times one month prior.

Post-test: With the intervention, the use of contraceptive increased to 874 (99.7%) – condom (99.6%), Pills (17.8%), depo (38.9%), Copper T (6.1%), Implant (12.1%) and female sterilization (2.4%). 675 (77.1%) used both condoms and one other contraceptive. 91.6 % reported consistent condom use. Only 8 (0.9%) reported using ECP 1 time in the last month.

Conclusion: The Community-based outreach (peer to peer) approach is effective in improving use of contraception among FSWs. The national SRH program should recognized the proven approach and employ it to reach marginalized and hard to reach populations.

16:10

Hall1

Use of contraceptive methods among young married women in Nepal

Kamala Devi Lamichhane

Central Department of Population Studies, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

Abstract

Nepal has a fairly high adolescent fertility rate and low use of contraception. Lack of contraceptive use is a major contributor to the high rates of unintended pregnancies amongst youth. There is also lack of specific study dealing with contraceptive behavior among young married women. This study examines the use and determinants of contraceptive methods over the time period of 15 years (2001–2016) among young married women in Nepal. Trend and bi-variate analysis of this study is based on the Nepal Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS), 2001, 2006, 2011 and 2016 data. The multivariate analysis is based on NDHS 2016 data of 2059 currently married non-pregnant young women aged 15–24 years. Logistic regression is used to assess the net effect of independent variables on dependent variable. The study shows that the contraceptive prevalence rate of young married women is only 34 percent. Number of living children, spousal separation, husband education, women's occupation, wealth status, caste/ethnic affiliation, fertility preference, decision making status, ideal number of children they prefer and media exposure are statistically associated to the use of contraception among young married women in Nepal. There is a need to strengthen income generating activities so as to improve young women's socio-economic status which will translate into female economic and social empowerment hence ability to discuss sexuality related issues. Family planning programmes should be designed so as to address the contraceptive needs of young women especially the low parity and Muslim adolescents.

Barriers and facilitators to use of family planning services among adolescents in Arghakhanchi: qualitative findings

Tripti Dhakal¹, Ashmin Hari Bhattarai¹

¹ADRA Nepal

Abstract

Background: Early marriage and pregnancy among adolescents in districts like Arghakhanchi of Nepal still place them and their children exposed to various health risks. Around 25% of adolescents in Nepal are already married or in union and unmet need for FP among adolescents is 35% (NDHS 2016). Uptake of contraception among adolescents is persistently low despite regular efforts from Government of Nepal in improving women's sexual and reproductive health. Majority of our family planning interventions focus on the general people, few on poor and vulnerable people leaving the adolescents poorly addressed. As a result, adolescents often come across significant hidden barriers to access FP services. This paper aims to present the barriers and facilitators to use of family planning service among adolescents in Arghakhanchi district.

Methodology: This was a qualitative study using the information generated during Rupantaran TOT and Rupantaran workshop in different places of Arghakhanchi district. Total 15 adolescent girls participated in Rupantaran TOT and 120 adolescent girls participated in 4 batches of Rupantaran orientation workshop. The workshops were conducted from 27th January to 22nd February 2019. Discussion sessions and roleplays were conducted in groups to gather information on family planning, methods, barriers and facilitators to use of family planning services.

Findings: We interacted with adolescents of Arghakhanchi district and identified some barriers contributing to low uptake of contraception among them as: husbands as migrant workers, lack of knowledge on FP methods, low decision-making role for marriage, lack of separate space in family house, confidentiality and privacy in service site and opening hours of health facility. The participants identified making separate space, maintaining confidentiality and privacy in service site, flexible service hours in HF specially for adolescents as major facilitators to improve access and utilization of FP services among adolescents.

Conclusion: Findings highlight the need of adolescent friendly service centers that adopt the facilitators identified in the study and address the barriers that obstruct adolescent from accessing FP services in health facilities.

16:30

Hall1

Contraceptive Choices and Determinants of Low Uptake of Long Acting Reversible Contraceptives by Young People (15–24 Years) in Nepal

Sujit Kumar Sah¹, Amit Dhungel², Ishwar Nath Mishra¹, Prapti Sedhain¹,
Dr. Ghanshyam Kumar Bhatta¹
¹ADRA Nepal, ²UNFPA Nepal

Abstract

Background: According to Nepal Demographic Health Survey 2016, despite Nepal's relatively high contraceptive prevalence rate (53%), around a quarter (23.6%) of married women still have an unmet need for FP. Married young couples could use long acting reversible contraceptive (LARC), to limit number of their children. However, use of Intra-uterine contraceptive devices (IUCD) and implant is very low as compared to short acting methods in Nepal.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out between October and November 2018 in 30 rural and urban municipalities of 15 districts representing five provinces- 1, 2, 3, 5 and 7 of Nepal. Mixed methods were adopted. 1635 youths were interviewed and Key Informant Interview (KII) with Health Service Providers and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were also performed. Data were collected through tablets/mobile using ODK application (KoBo). Data were analyzed by using SPSS and At.Lasti Software.

Results: Higher proportion of women knew about LARC methods than men - Implant (80.4% vs 52.3%) and IUCD (67.2% vs. 39.8%). Out of the total responders 20.9% were using FP methods out of which 12% and 1.2% were using Implant and IUCD respectively. The logistic regress analysis shows that current use of FP was relatively higher among Brahmin/Chhetri caste ethnicity (OR 2.07, CI 1.21 to 3.55), marriage age 20 years and above (OR 2.04, CI 1.29 to 3.21), had one child (OR 9.97, CI 4.58 to 21.73) and two children (OR 2.23, CI 1.17 to 4.25) than with other groups of respondents.

Conclusion: Strategy and guidelines should be incorporated into current federal structure for smooth implementation of the program activities.

PARALLEL SESSION

Sub-theme : Demand generation and behavior change

Chair : Mahendra Prasad Shrestha,
Chief, HCD, MoHP

Co-chair : Netra Prasad Bhatta,
Sr. Program Specialist-FP/RH, USAID

 Hall 2

Integration of the Standard Days Method (Malachakra), a fertility awareness method, for women in marginalized communities of Rupandehi

Naramaya Subba Limbu¹, Nokafu K. Sandra Chipanta¹, Christina Riley¹,
Khem Narayan Pokhrel¹, Sarah Thompson¹, Sangita Khatri², Dominick Shattuck¹

¹Institute for Reproductive Health, Georgetown University, ²Save the Children Nepal

Abstract

Background: Multiple factors limit women's use of modern contraception, including: access, misconceptions about fertility and method side-effects. From 2017 – 2018, the Standard Days Method (SDM), a natural fertility awareness-based method that utilizes CycleBeads (Malachakra) was integrated into 32 VDCs of Rupandehi. The collaboration between FWD, DPHO, and the FACT Project rigorously monitored and evaluated this process to understand acceptability, provide counseling guidance, and correct use by clients.

Methods: Evaluating this process, the team administered the Knowledge Improvement Tool to 51 service providers and 74 Malachakra users. This was complemented by an endline mixed-methods survey among a systematically selected 338 men and 561 women.

Results: Monitoring data revealed that 88% of Malachakra users continued use after 3 months. Almost all users (97%) reported being able to use condoms or abstain from sex during the fertile days, and 82% reported husband support. Counselors scores ranged from 85-100% proficiency of counseling for Malachakra. Among Malachakra users (n=68) at end line survey, 62.9% of men and 53% of women reported their intention to continue using the method. Despite benefits touted by users, the overall uptake was 423.

Lesson learned: Malachakra was woven into the existing FP method mix in Rupandehi with varied success. The method appealed to some marginalized communities, but awareness and uptake would benefit from additional promotion and demand generation activities where it is available. Furthermore, now Malachakra app is available on mobile phones for free download.

16:10

Hall2

Using Entertainment-Education to motivate FP Use

Rajan Parajuli
Population Media Center-Nepal

Abstract

Background: According to Nepal Demographic Health Survey 2016, despite Nepal's relatively high contraceptive prevalence rate (53%), around a quarter (23.6%) of married women still have an unmet need for FP. Married young couples could use long acting reversible contraceptive (LARC), to limit number of their children. However, use of Intra-uterine contraceptive devices (IUCD) and implant is very low as compared to short acting methods in Nepal.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out between October and November 2018 in 30 rural and urban municipalities of 15 districts representing five provinces- 1, 2, 3, 5 and 7 of Nepal. Mixed methods were adopted. 1635 youths were interviewed and Key Informant Interview (KII) with Health Service Providers and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were also performed. Data were collected through tablets/mobile using ODK application (KoBo). Data were analyzed by using SPSS and At.Lasti Software.

Results: Higher proportion of women knew about LARC methods than men - Implant (80.4% vs 52.3%) and IUCD (67.2% vs. 39.8%). Out of the total responders 20.9% were using FP methods out of which 12% and 1.2% were using Implant and IUCD respectively. The logistic regress analysis shows that current use of FP was relatively higher among Brahmin/Chhetri caste ethnicity (OR 2.07, CI 1.21 to 3.55), marriage age 20 years and above (OR 2.04, ci 1.29 to 3.21), had one child (OR 9.97, CI 4.58 to 21.73) and two children (OR 2.23, CI 1.17 to 4.25) than with other groups of respondents.

Conclusion: Strategy and guidelines should be incorporated into current federal structure for smooth implementation of the program activities.

16:20

Hall 2

Awareness and Practice of Family Planning Services among Married Women of Reproductive Age in a Rural Municipality of Saptari District, Nepal

Reena Bhagat¹, Ratna Kumari Maharjan¹

¹Patan Academy of Health Sciences, School of Midwifery and Nursing, Nepal

Abstract

Introduction: One in three maternal deaths can be avoided if all women have met need for family planning services. Contraceptive Prevalence Rate (CPR) among currently married women age 15-49 years in Nepal is 43% using modern methods. On average, fertility is higher among women in rural areas than in urban areas and by province, high in province 2. The objective of this study was to assess the awareness and practice of family planning services among married women of reproductive age in a Rural Municipality of Saptari district, Nepal.

Methodology: Cross-sectional study with multi (two) stage sampling technique through face-to-face interview technique using structured interview schedule in Maithili version was done including 280 samples by researcher herself. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed using SPSS version 16.0 software for data analysis.

Results: The findings of the study revealed that 91.78% respondents had adequate awareness regarding family planning services whereas only 59.64% of respondent were current FP users. Out of which majority practiced female sterilization and only 39(23.35%) used temporary methods. Most common reason for not using temporary FP methods included side effects (90%). Level of awareness of respondents was not found statistically significant with their practice regarding family planning services.

Conclusion: It was concluded that majority of respondents had adequate awareness regarding family planning services, but their practice was comparatively low. FP methods were practiced only for limiting purpose rather than birth spacing. Correct information and proper counselling are of vital importance in reducing the misconceptions regarding contraceptives use.

16:30

Hall2

A formative Research on understanding the situation and identifying needs, preference and enabling and impeding behaviors in among poor and marginalized women 9 districts of Nepal

Sudeepa Khanal¹, Sanjeev Kumar Sahani¹, Raman Shrestha², Suresh Mehata³
¹Ipas Nepal, ²Marie Stopes International/SPN Nepal, ³Ministry of Health and Population, Nepal

Abstract

Background: Factors influencing family planning (FP) preferences, demand and use are multifaceted. The factors are highly context-and population-dependent and consequently contribute to inequities in demand for, access to, and use of FP services.

Objective of the study: To identify the needs, preferences of poor, hard to reach and marginalized women and girls and understand their enabling and impending behavior for accessing and using FP services.

Methods: Qualitative method was used to gain understanding about both demand and supply side context and get insights to barriers and facilitators for FP services. 72 SSI and KII and 9 FGD were conducted with various categories of men and women in the nine districts.

Findings: The study clearly shows inconsistent information and lack of in-depth understanding about different FP methods despite having heard of them indicating the need to develop context specific interventions. The study also identifies group specific beliefs, myths and misconceptions, decision making processes, communication between partners among others and health system factors including the effect of federalization on FP service delivery affecting its use.

Conclusion: The detailed and context specific information from various categories of respondents (migrants, adolescents, marginalized communities among others) could be used as an evidence base to develop more contextual appropriate and responsive interventions and strengthen FP demand generation activities to address the problem of low use of contraception among poor, hard to reach and marginalized women and girls.

08:30-09:00	Registration – Lobby
09:00-10:30	Plenary Session 2 – Hall 1
	<p>Reaching the Unreached</p> <p>Presenters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kabita Aryal, CNA, FWD - Unreached population, policies and programs..... • Deepak Karki, Health Advisor, DFID - Achievements, issues, challenges and way forward: focusing unreached population <p>Moderator: Aarti Chataut</p> <p>Panelists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tahir Hussain, Muslim Social Leader • Deepa Pradhan, FPAN • Ram Chandra Gaire, BYAN • Uma Koirala – FCHV, Sunsari • Bhogendra Raj Dotel – Director, Health Directorate, Province 1
10:30-11:00	Refreshment Break
11:00-11:45	Plenary Session 3 – Hall 1
	<p>Adding it up: Costs and benefits of meeting the contraceptive and maternal and newborn health needs of women in Nepal</p> <p>Presenters: Dr. Aparna Sundaram & Dr. Mahesh Puri (Special Session of CREHPA and Guttmacher Institute)</p> <p>Chair: Dilli Raman Adhikari</p>

11:45-12:45	Parallel Session 5 - Hall 1	Parallel Session 6 - Hall 2
	<p>Expanding access to quality FP Services</p> <p>Chair: Dr. Dipendra Raman Singh, Chief, QARD, MoHP</p> <p>Co-chair: Dr. Josue Orellana, Director-Health & Nutrition, ADRA-I</p> <p>Presenters:</p> <p>Matthew Moroni Investigating the quality of family planning counselling as part of routine antenatal care and its effectiveness among women in Nepal: a hospital-based qualitative study</p> <p>Mona Sharma Introduction of Mobile application in Sangini Quality Assurance Programme</p> <p>Chetraj Pandit Assessment of the Integration of Family Planning & Expanded Programme of Immunization (EPI) in Selected Districts of Nepal 2017</p> <p>Prapti Sedhain Balanced Counselling Increased the Acceptance of Long Acting Reversible Contraceptives in Nepal</p>	<p>Systems strengthening for FP services</p> <p>Chair: Dr. Senendra Raj Upreti, Former Acting DG, DoHS, MoHP, Nepal</p> <p>Co-chair: Nichola Cadge, International Health Advisor, DFID Nepal</p> <p>Presenters:</p> <p>Dr Roshani Amatya Strengthening Quality Improvement system In Family Planning Services</p> <p>Ashmin Hari Bhattarai Improving family planning service delivery and contraceptive uptake: experience from "Family Planning Service Strengthening Program"</p> <p>Basant Thapa Strengthening Family Planning and HIV Service Integration in Non-Governmental Organization Healthcare Settings: Experience from USAID-funded Saath-Saath Project</p> <p>Indra Bilas Baral Institutional Systems and Capacities of Municipalities and Health Facilities to Deliver Family Planning Services</p>
12:45-14:00	Lunch Break & Poster Exhibition	
14:00-15:30	Plenary Session 4 – Hall 1	
	<p>FP in changed context</p> <p>Presenter: Dr. Guna Nidhi Sharma, Senior Health Administrator PPMD, MoHP - FP financing: Resource generation and mobilization</p> <p>Moderator: Dr. Khem Bahadur Karki</p> <p>Panelists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Pushpa Chaudhary, Health Secretary • Dr. Pramod Yadav, Director, Health Directorate, Province 2 • Dr. Gunaraj Awasthi, Director, Health Directorate, Province 7 • Deepak Karki, Health Advisor, DFID • Netra P. Bhatta, Sr. Program Specialist-FP/RH, USAID • Goma Giri Achrya, Deputy Mayor, Butwal Sub-Metropolitan city • Ram Narayan Chaudhary, Health Coordinator, Kataari Municipality 	
15:30-16:30	Refreshment Break	
16:30-17:30	Closing Ceremony	

PLENARY SESSION 2

Reaching the Unreached

🕒 09:00 - 10:30 📍 Hall 1

Moderator and Panelists	Topics	Presenter
Moderator: Aarti Chataut Panelists: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tahir Hussain, Muslim Social Leader • Deepa Pradhan, FPAN • Ram Chandra Gaire, BYAN • Uma Koirala – FCHV, Sunsari • Bhogendra Raj Dotel – Director, Health Directorate, Province 1 	Unreached population, policies and programs Achievements, issues, challenges and way forward: focusing unreached population	Kabita Aryal, CNA, FWD Deepak Karki, Health Advisor, DFID

Biography

Kabita Aryal is working as a Community Nursing Administrator under Ministry of Health and Population (MoHP). Presently, she has taken the responsibility of section chief of Family Planning and Reproductive Health at Family Welfare Division, under Department of Health Services. Professionally, she has gained sound experience in the Public health sector since 2004 AD. She has completed MSc Nursing in Community Health and Master in Arts (MA) in Rural Development. She is competent in training activities, research, program planning,

implementation and monitoring which she gained by working at various organizations (Government, I/NGOS and academic institutions). While working at MoHP and DoHS, she has contributed in drafting and finalization of different health related polices and strategies including Family planning and Reproductive health.

Deepak Karki is a public health practitioner in health systems and policy, sexual and reproductive health, including HIV and Tuberculosis, health programme management, monitoring & evaluation, surveillance and research. Currently he is working as Health Advisor at UK Department for International Development (DFID) in Nepal.

PLENARY SESSION 3

**Adding it up:
Costs and benefits of meeting the contraceptive,
maternal and newborn health needs of women in
Nepal**

 Hall 1

Chair	Topics	Presenter
Chair: Dilli Raman Adhikari	Adding it up: Costs and benefits of meeting the contraceptive, maternal and newborn health needs of women in Nepal	Dr. Aparna Sundaram, Guttmacher Institute & Dr. Mahesh Puri, CREHPA

Biography

Dr Mahesh Puri is Associate Director of the Centre for Research on Environment Health and Population Activities (CREHPA) – national non-profit research organization based in Kathmandu, Nepal. Dr. Puri has been actively involved in the areas of reproductive and sexual health and rights including gender-based violence related research studies and program for more than 17 years in Nepal. His areas of expertise are on mixing of qualitative and quantitative research methods in researching sensitive topics of reproductive and sexual health and rights. His current research focuses on family planning, maternal and child health, adolescent health and development gender-based violence, unintended pregnancy and abortion and non-communicable diseases. He has extensive experiences to engage concerned national level stakeholders in the research process and results uptake.

Dr. Aparna Sundaram is a Senior Research Scientist at the Guttmacher Institute, New York, USA. In addition to this analysis on Nepal, she has worked on estimating the costs and benefits of expanding contraceptive use in Uganda, Ethiopia and Burkina Faso. Dr Sundaram has also worked on estimating abortion incidence in India and Nepal, and on estimating contraceptive failure rates for the United States.

PARALLEL SESSION 5

Sub-theme : Expanding access to quality FP services

Chair : Dr. Dipendra Raman Singh,
Chief, QARD, MoHP

Co-chair : Dr. Josue Orellana,
Director-Health & Nutrition, ADRA-I

 Hall 1

Investigating the quality of family planning counselling as part of routine antenatal care and its effectiveness among women in Nepal: a hospital-based qualitative study

Mahesh Puri¹, Matthew Moroni², Erin Pearson³, Elina Pradhan⁴, Iqbal Shah⁵
¹Center for Research on Environment Health and Population Activities (CREHPA), Nepal,
²Lund University, Sweden, ³Ipas, United States, ⁴The World Bank Group, Nepal,
⁵Harvard T. H. Chan School of Public Health, United States

Abstract

Background: Integration of counselling on family planning (FP) at the time of antenatal care (ANC) and delivery has the potential to increase post-partum contraceptive use. This study investigates the quality of postpartum FP counselling services and its effectiveness among women who had at least two ANC visits.

Methods: In-depth interviews were conducted with 24 women who had at least two ANC visits in one of the six tertiary public hospitals receiving an intervention to integrate FP counselling in maternity care services and introduce postpartum intrauterine device (PPIUD) insertion in the immediate postpartum period. Data were collected as part of an evaluation of this intervention in Nepal. In-depth interviews were audio recorded, transcribed in Nepali, and translated into English and analyzed thematically.

Results: Overall, the quality of FP counselling during ANC was unsatisfactory based on patient expectations and perceptions of interaction with providers, and FP methods offered, including offer of PPIUD. Reasons for dissatisfaction with counselling services included very crowded environment, short time with the provider, non-availability of provider, long waiting times, limited number of days ANC services, non-receipt and lack of comprehension of FP related IEC materials. Women visiting hospitals with a dedicated FP counselor reported higher quality of FP counselling.

Conclusions: There is an urgent need to re-visit the format of counselling, IEC materials, setting, and to strengthen availability and interaction with providers during counselling during ANC services to improve quality of and satisfaction with FP counselling during ANC visits, and ultimately improve women's access to post-partum FP in Nepal.

11:5

Hall 1

Introduction of Mobile application in Sangini Quality Assurance Programme

Mona Sharma¹, Rajesh Bhagat¹

¹Nepal CRS Company

Abstract

Background: In 1994, CRS was the first organization in the world to provide the three monthly 'Sangini' Depomedroxyprogesterone (DMPA) injectable contraceptives through private clinic and pharmacies as social franchising network that introduced Family Planning, Reproductive Health and Maternal-Child Health services. Now, there are more than 3300 pharmacies across Nepal under the Sangini Network. CRS initiated its Quality Assurance program to Sangini service providers in 2016 with a model of conducting Technical Support Visits (TSV) using Quality Assurance Officers (QAOs). QAOs conduct regular TSV to collect relevant service delivery information and verify conformity to standards and provide on-sight technical support. The mobile application is being used to replace the hard copy data collection in Sangini quality assurance program

Objectives: Record data of Sangini outlet through web based mobile application. Get real time data for instant feedback to Sangini service provider on quality improvement. Use consolidated reports of non-compliance by service providers to plan and implement the targeted interventions.

Methodologies: Mobile application used as tool for technical support visit data collection and analysis. Java and MySQL database software was used for generating the result. Results: QAOs collected data of technical support visits in mobile and in hardcopy. The results generated by the mobile application and by hardcopy matched. With this validation, CRS is fully implementing the use of the mobile application for TSV data collection.

Recommendation: Use of mobile applications has increased the efficacy of TSV to monitor the quality of Sangini providers.

12:05

Hall 1

Assessment of the Integration of Family Planning & Expanded Programme of Immunization (EPI) in Selected Districts of Nepal 2017

Chetraj Pandit
Family Welfare Division, Nepal

Abstract

Background: Mothers need to practice contraception to space births at least two-year apart; In Nepal, immunization programme has the highest coverage rate; objectives are to Explore if the FP/EPI integration brings about change in FP and EPI outcomes.

Methodology: Qualitative information collected from DHOs/DPHOs (4), FP (4) and EPI (4) focal persons by conducting Klls =12 at district level, In-charges (8), FP /EPI Service Providers (static (8) and outreach (8)) and FCHVs (8) from 8 sites interviewed. Quantitative data collected by administering structured questionnaire to 64 mothers Result: The median age of mothers interviewed was 23, About 9% mothers adolescents; about 56% belonged to age group 20-24, Most mothers belonged to Bahun/ Chhetri/ Sanyashi category (69%), about 27% belonged to Dalit and 5% Janajti, Most (97%) mothers attended Group Counselling on FP when they visited FP/EPI clinics, 70% mothers counselled by vaccinators and the rest by nurses/ANMs; and Only 5% mothers accepted FP method at 1st visit FP clients using Depo & pills of regular static clinics increasingly declining while that of the FP/ EPI intervention clinics are continually rising, monthly FP methods – pills and Depo uptake. A considerable increase in the uptake of two spacing methods noted, marginalized groups (27%) making use of FP service than their share (22%) in the total population, no decline in immunization uptake even after integrating FP service with regular EPI services.

Conclusion: Integration of the Family planning and Immunization is best way to improve both programs, its cost effective program for hard to reach population.

12:15

Hall 1

Balanced Counselling Increased the Acceptance of Long Acting Reversible Contraceptives in Nepal

Ishwar Nath Mishra¹ Amit Dhungel², Sujit Kumar Sah¹, Prapti Sedhain¹,
Dr. Ghanshyam Kumar Bhatta¹
¹ADRA Nepal, ²UNFPA Nepal

Abstract

background: Nepal aims for a modern contraceptive prevalence rate (mCPR) of 52% by 2020 (NHSS-IP 2016-21). Though FP unmet need in most groups except adolescents and the poorest quintile declined from 27% in 2011 to 24% in 2016, use of modern contraceptives has stagnated since 2011 at 43% mCPR. Poor systemic focus on quality, comprehensive, and very importantly client-friendly FP services are among the key factors contributing to stagnation (NDHS 2016). ADRA Nepal tested client-friendly approach of FP programming in four districts to increase modern contraceptive usage. During January to December 2017, the project adopted innovative strategies to create both demand and supply among minority groups through mobilization of 20 trained Visiting Service Providers (VSPs).

Methodology: A quantitative interventional study using routine program data from four districts of Nepal where Family Planning System Strengthening Program (FPSSP) has been implementing. 131 Government Health Facilities were visited, and clients were approached to balanced counseling for the period of 12 month (January to December 2017). Data were recorded first in the Service Statistics Register and later transferred to Microsoft-Excel for analysis and interpretation.

Results: LARC uptake increased by 5.6% (LARC: 3124 in 2016 to 3311 in 2017) among new users and proportion among adolescents <20 years (2.8% to 4.7%). Out of 4910 clients who were approached to balanced counseling more than two third (67.4%) clients accepted LARC.

Conclusion: Voluntary participation and informed choice achieved through balanced counselling is a powerful way to reach clients who may not otherwise seek FP.

PARALLEL SESSION

Sub-theme : Systems strengthening for FP services

Chair : Dr. Senendra Raj Upreti, Former DG, DoHS, MoHP

Co-chair : Nichola Cadge,
International Health Advisor, DFID Nepal

 Hall 2

Strengthening Quality Improvement system In Family Planning Services

Dr. Roshani Amatya¹, Basanti Chand², Dr Rajendra Bhadra²

¹Jhpiego Nepal, ²Former Jhpiego Nepal

Abstract

Background: Though FP services expanded to remote corners of the country, it has not been accompanied by quality. Facility readiness and providers' skills has always been issue along with a system to look into the quality of services at point of care.

Objective: Strengthening existing health system by empowering HF/HFOMCs to improve quality of FP services by addressing identified performance problems locally.

Process: Health Facility Quality Improvement (HFQI) system was introduced in 1113 HFs and integrated with local health governance and its 7-step planning. HF QI teams assessed using QI tools to identify QI gaps, prepared action plans and HFOMCs worked with local government to address gaps systematically. Technical assistance from H4L (Jhpiego) led HFOMCs to be more responsive, accountable and increasingly capable of addressing it in collaboration with stakeholders.

Findings: Implementation as per the action plan led to improvement in QoC i.e. compliance with standards. For example; subsequent assessments showed compliance with standard of FP counseling increased to nearly 100% and availability of National Medical Standards - Contraceptives improved from 31% in baseline to 70.5% in endline.

Village/Municipality Annual Plans included activities to address gaps of QI assessment and allocation of budget. For example, in 14 districts Rs 49.41 million for FP and QI budget for FY 17/18.

Conclusion: Simple but detail QI tools allowed HF staffs to assess quality of FP services. Resources could be generated if HFOMC/Local Government is engaged and gaps could be addressed by locally generated fund along with funds allocated from management division which help in sustainability.

11:55

Hall 2

Improving family planning service delivery and contraceptive uptake: experience from “Family Planning Service Strengthening Program”

Ashmin Hari Bhattarai¹, Ishwar Nath Mishra¹, Sujit Kumar Sah¹,
Dr. Ghanashyam Kumar Bhatta¹
¹ADRA Nepal

Abstract

Background: Despite the availability of free family planning (FP) services through government health facilities in Nepal, the modern contraceptive prevalence rate (mCPR) remained stagnant at 43% in the country since 2011 and is just 39% in Province 5 (NDHS 2016). We implemented Family Planning Service Strengthening Program (FPSSP) in four districts namely Kapilvastu, Rupandehi, Arghakhanchi and Pyuthan of Province 5 in the year 2018. This project intervention involved: family planning services delivery through Visiting Service Providers (VSP), capacity development of service providers, advocacy and stakeholder engagement at various levels. This paper reports findings from the project intervention in selected districts of Province 5 at an early stage of the project.

Methodology: This paper was developed based on the project findings reported from four districts where project has been implemented during August to December 2018. All records of FP users recorded in Service Statistic Register were reviewed and required information was collected. Microsoft Excel was used for data analysis and interpretation. Other regular project reports and event reports were reviewed for additional information.

Results: Over a 6-months period, the project contributed to considerable demand raise for family planning, evidenced in increased long-acting reversible contraceptive (LARC) uptake. The number of females receiving LARC service each month in the project area via VSPs remarkably increased from 145 in August to 626 in December. Out of 1740 clients receiving LARC service during the project period, almost half (48%) were from the population with high unmet need and those farthest behind: Dalit, Madhesi and Muslim.

The project improved the capacity of family planning service providers through trainings on LARC service, ASRH, use of DMT & MEC wheel, and Basic Health Logistic and Procurement System. It also secured the commitment of Provincial ministry (7% of the total health budget by Province 2, 5 and 7) on the investments in family planning.

Conclusion: Integration of demand generation interventions, mobilization of VSPs and capacity development of health workers evidently increased FP service uptake in the community. This project successfully demonstrated the possibility of engaging government stakeholders to commit for investment in family planning.

12:05

Hall 2

Strengthening Family Planning and HIV Service Integration in Non-Governmental Organization Healthcare Settings: Experience from USAID-funded Saath-Saath Project

Basant Thapa¹, Bhagawan Shrestha¹, Satish Raj Pandey²
¹FHI 360 Nepal, ²FHI 360 Nigeria

Abstract

Background: In Nepal, HIV prevalence among adults aged 15–49 is 0.15%, and at the end of 2017, an estimated were living with HIV (PLHIV). Female sex workers (FSWs) and PLHIV tend to have unduly high rates of unintended pregnancy. Integrating family planning (FP) services into HIV activities can increase access to FP information and services to FSWs and PLHIV.

Methodology: SSP trained 5,390 FP and HIV service providers on FP/HIV-related topics to enhance their capacity to provide quality key populations (KPs)-friendly services. FP/HIV integrated services were provided to FSWs & their clients, PLHIV, and also migrants & their spouses in some selected sites, through 39 NGO-run service delivery sites in 26 districts. SSP ensured availability of necessary job aids, equipment and timely supply of logistics, including FP commodities, at designated service sites for integrated services through the national logistics supply chain mechanism.

Results: From August 2012 to June 2016, 46,995 clients received FP counseling (36% were FSWs and 64% were PLHIV and other KPs), and of these, 23,260 (29% were FSWs and 71% were PLHIV and other KPs) received contraceptive methods including condoms from SSP supported NGO service delivery sites, contributing 261,592 cumulative couple years of protection. A total of 3,572 (15% of 23,260) people adopted non-condom FP methods (oral contraceptive pills, injectable, Implant and IUD) during the period, of which 76% were FSWs and 24% were PLHIV and other KPs.

Conclusion: It is feasible to scale-up integrated FP/HIV services in HIV service delivery platforms. FP services can be incorporated with little additional training and commodities, and KPs-specific FP/HIV service-related capacity building of health care providers helped to promote KPs friendly and sensitive services. Greater innovative approaches continue to be needed to improve the adoption of condom, and non-condom FP methods among KPs in Nepal.

12:15

Hall 2

Institutional Systems and Capacities of Municipalities and Health Facilities to Deliver Family Planning Services

Indra Bilas Baral¹, Deepak Paudel¹, Hom Nath Subedi², Madav Chaulagain², Samikshya Singh², Pravin Paudel²

¹Strengthening Systems for Better Health, Save the Children, Nepal,

²Strengthening Systems for Better Health, Abt Associates, Nepal

Abstract

Background: USAID's Strengthening Systems for Better Health Activity is designed to support the Government of Nepal in their efforts to improve health outcomes, particularly for the country's most marginalized and disadvantaged groups. The project carried out participatory assessments of health systems and capacity at municipal and health facility levels to identify, prioritize and customize delivery of technical assistance to improve availability and quality of health services.

Methodologies: The assessment was designed to provide systematic information on the current status of health systems functions and capacity at municipal and health facility levels in relation to legal and policy arrangements, institutional arrangements, planning and budgeting, human resources, information management, medicines and supplies, governance and readiness of facilities to deliver selected maternal, newborn and child health and family planning services. The assessments were done from December 2018 through February 2019 in 39/105 municipalities and 137/480 peripheral health facilities in Karnali Province and Banke, Bardia and Dang by trained Activity staff, using standard tools.

Results: Very few peripheral health facilities were providing all five temporary family planning methods (condom, pills, Depo, Implant and IUD). Reasons for not delivering all five methods were not having trained human resource, lack of proper counselling rooms, commodity shortages and lack of IEC materials. Only eight out of the municipalities assessed had at least one facility providing all five modern, temporary methods, and in the majority of these facilities, IEC materials were not adequate.

Conclusion: The assessment showed a critical need to support municipalities and health facilities to strengthen their systems to improve service availability and quality of FP and MNCH services. This will be addressed through the process of developing necessary policies, systems, procedures and standards at local and provincial level through adaptation of national policies, systems, procedures and standards, and working with provincial and local governments to help expand the number providers with the skills necessary to provide quality family planning services.

PLENARY SESSION 4

FP in changed context

14:00 - 15:30

Hall 2

Moderator and Panelists	Topic	Presenter
<p>Moderator: Dr. Khem Bahadur Karki</p> <p>Panelists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Pushpa Chaudhary, Health Secretary • Dr. Pramod Yadav, Director, Health Directorate, Province 2 • Dr. Gunaraj Awasthi, Director, Health Directorate, Province 7 • Deepak Karki, Health Advisor, DFID • Netra P. Bhatta, Sr. Program Specialist-FP/RH, USAID • Ram Narayan Chaudhary, Health Coordinator, Kataari Municipality • Goma Giri Acharya, Deputy Mayor, Butwal Sub-Metropolitan city 	<p>FP financing: resource generation and mobilization</p>	<p>Dr. Guna Nidhi Sharma, Senior Health Administrator, MoHP</p>

Biography

Dr. Guna Nidhi Sharma currently works as Senior Health Administrator in Ministry of Health and Population of Nepal. Dr. Sharma has almost thirteen years of experience working with different national and international organizations, predominantly in Nepal. His expertise revolves around five major areas of medical and public health programmes - Epidemiology, Disaster Management, Tuberculosis, Refugee health assessment and Emergency medical care.

FP-EPI integration activities sensitize local government for investment in family planning: a local level experience from Udayapur district

Abinash Bhatta¹, Ashmin Hari Bhattarai¹
¹ADRA Nepal

Abstract

Background: Although government and other partner organizations are making regular efforts to strengthen FP service delivery in the district, modern contraceptive prevalence rate (mCPR) is in decreasing trend since last two fiscal years in Udayapur district of Nepal. It was 21% in the fiscal year 2073/74 with high unmet need for family planning (FP). There were no visible investments by local government for family planning activities. FP-EPI is considered as an effective model to improve CPR through increase in contraceptive uptake. This study assessed the impact of FP-EPI integration activities in relation to investment for FP by local government.

Methodology: Qualitative study was done to study the impact of FP-EPI integration activities conducted in support of ADRA Nepal in January 2018. FP-EPI integration DToT was conducted in Udayapur district for two days for HF level coordinator and sub-coordinator in December 2018. One day FP-EPI integration activities was conducted for local stakeholders and elected representatives. Follow-up visit was done to different municipalities and rural-municipalities to assess the commitment and allocation by local government for family planning related activities.

Results: The impact of FP-EPI integration DToT and orientation workshop was seen in the commitment of investment for FP by Katari Municipality. The social development committee of Katari Municipality has allocated NRs. 500000 (Five Hundred Thousand Rupees) for conduction of FP-EPI integration activities.

“We have made decision to allocate the budget for FP-EPI activities funded amount Rs. 5,00,000 for Katari Municipality. Decision has been made by Social development committee. (Samajik Bikas Samiti).”- Ram Narayan Chaudhary (Health coordinator)

Conclusion: FP-EPI integration activities enabled local government to realize the need of family planning activities and invest for the same. This can be replicated to other similar settings to generate commitment and investment from local government.

Factors affecting utilization of family planning methods among the reproductive age women of Prabat

Sharada Sapkota¹, Alisha Rijal², Sita Rijal³

¹Government of Nepal, Baglung, ²Yeti Health Science Academy, Nepal,

³OM Health Campus, Nepal

Abstract

Background: Usage of family planning services in developing countries have been found to avert unintended pregnancies, reduce maternal and child mortality, however, it's usage still remains low. The objective of this study is to identify the factors affecting utilization of family planning methods among the reproductive age women.

Methodologies: A descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted among 106 reproductive age women of Shalija VDC of Parbat district, Nepal. Non probability purposive sampling technique was adopted to select the sample by using interview guided questionnaire. Data was analyzed by using descriptive (mean, standard deviation) and inferential analysis (chi-square test) with SPSS version 21.

Result: The mean age of the 106 participants of study was 35.21 years. Family planning utilization among reproductive age women was 36.8%. Majority of them preferred using Inj. Depo-provera (34.9%). There is statistically significant association of the utilization of family planning methods and the educational status and occupation of husband and wife, total number of children and ethnicity. Majority of respondents (84.6%) stated that they were using family planning methods to prevent unwanted pregnancy. The major reason for discontinuation of the use of family planning methods was due to related side effects (58.2%).

Conclusion: The study showed that utilization of family planning methods were affected by various factors.

Recommendation: An interventional health education could work to reduce factors affecting the utilization of family planning methods among reproductive age women.

Unmet need for modern family planning among married women living with HIV in Nepal

Bhagawan Shrestha¹, Kiran Bam¹, Durga Prasad Bhandari¹

¹LINKAGES Nepal Project, FHI360 Nepal

Abstract

Background: The Government of Nepal (GoN) aims to enable women/couples to have the desired family size with healthy timing and spacing of pregnancies by improving access to family planning (FP) services and reducing unmet need for modern contraceptives. Similarly, GoN aims to eliminate vertical transmission of HIV. Prevention of unintended pregnancies among women living with HIV (WLHIV) is one of the strategies for preventing mother-to-child transmission of HIV. However, one fourth of women in Nepal have unmet need for FP. This study assessed the unmet need for FP among married WLHIV in Nepal.

Methodologies: This cross-sectional study included structured interviews with 328 married WLHIV (16-49 years) enrolled in HIV care at any of five antiretroviral treatment (ART) centers in Nepal between January-February 2016. Unmet need was measured using 23 different survey questions from Demographic and Health Surveys, 2011. FHI 360's ethical review board and Nepal Health Research Council approved the study.

Results: The unmet need of FP among WLHIV was 18%. The mean age was 34 years. The median age at first marriage and pregnancy was 17 and 19 years, respectively. About 64% had received FP counseling/education. In total, 78% of those with met needs were using condom and 12% had permanent sterilization.

Conclusion and recommendation: The unmet need of WLHIV was lower than general population, as most of the WLHIV were using condoms. Counseling on dual method use such as condom and other FP methods and access to a range of contraceptive methods should be provided as a part of HIV services.

Factors influencing utilization of family planning services among female of reproductive age in remote district, Achham , Nepal

Bharat Gotame Sharki¹, Bhawan Sing Kunwar²

¹UNFPA Nepal, ²District Health Office, Achham, Nepal

Abstract

Background: Despite the several efforts of Govern of Nepal to increase utilization of quality family planning services, its usage in remote areas is very low. CPR of Achham district is 30.04% (DHO Achham Rep: 2074/75) which is lower than the national average. This study aimed at examining factors influencing the utilization of family planning services among women of reproductive age (15-49 years) in Achham district.

Methods: A mix method using quantitative and qualitative questionnaire was used to interview s total of 200 women aged 15-49 from 200 sampled households. The quantitative data was analyzed using excel. For qualitative data, six focus groups discussions were conducted with service providers, family planning users and non-users, faith healers (Dhami jhakris). Exit interview with users were also conducted to assess the quality of services and satisfaction.

Results: The study showed that 34% of the women aged 15-49 had used family planning services before. Major motivating factors to usage of family planning services were to space children, 84%, education and employment 12%, and others 4 %. Major reasons for not accessing family planning services were opposition from husbands 87.5%, misconceptions about family planning, 46%, cultural norms 47%, knowledge on family planning methods and awareness 40.5%, access to FP services 45%, friendliness to staffs and confidentiality 24%.

Recommendations: Family planning awareness should be promoted to the households and family level focusing to male and also to address socio cultural norms. The government should also scale up quality family planning services focusing remote areas.

Community Based Integrated Approach of Delivering FP Services: A Case Study of Bayalpata Hospital

Bikash Gauchan¹, Bharat Gotame²

¹Nyaya Health Nepal, ²UNFPA Nepal

Abstract

The access to different methods of family planning (FP) services in rural areas of Nepal is not able to address the demand of people. People living in both rural and urban areas might not have access to information about all family planning methods and services. Bayalpata Hospital is run by Nyaya Health Nepal, a non-governmental organization, in a public private partnership (PPP) with Nepal's ministry of health and population to provide comprehensive integrated primary care and essential surgical services. One of the core functions of the comprehensive integrated primary care and essential surgical services is family planning services.

People living in rural areas still rely on short acting and long acting reversible contraceptives and may have access to permanent methods on camp basis which is organized infrequently. Public and private hospitals with 25 bed and above capacity must have all the options of family planning services like condoms, pills, depo injection, implant, IUCD, vasectomy and minilaparotomy (commonly called Minilap) as per the new safe motherhood and reproductive health bill passed by the parliamentarians and endorsed by the President of Nepal on 2nd Ashoj 2075. In addition to doctors and nurses, community health workers (CHWs) who are professionally trained and regularly mentored could be instrumental in expanding access to some of the family planning methods near the homes of mostly women and men in the communities. Bayalpata Hospital is serving the FP needs of people by providing all ranges of methods in addition to balanced counseling strategy (BCS), condom and pills distribution by CHWs in the communities.

Demand Generation- IPC through male

Chandra Gyawali
UNFPA Nepal

Abstract

Background: Family planning and reproductive health have been the priority health areas in Nepal more than two decades. Many programs have been implemented to increase awareness, access to, and use of FP and RH products and services, and much progress has been made. The overall population growth rate declined, and similarly, total fertility rate is also decreased though the contraceptive prevalence rate is still very low in Nepal by 50% and the millennium goal for 67%. By 2015.

The reasons behind the selection of Male for IPC, males are decision maker in the family no matter how much she educated or empowered. Their role is to create awareness among male members in the family so that they can support their wife to use it, strengthen the referral system in public and private health facilities with little more technical knowledge on Family Planning, extensive household visit and group discussion with male during social meetings. The assumption is that after six month of mobilization, family planning users will be increased automatically from those coverage areas.

Methodology: Before implementing male engagement, based line survey will be taken to Public and private health facilities to identify service flow with developing simple format mentioning some important indicators like Facility Registration, FP commodity supply and service, reporting channels etc.

Results: Male engagement will be increased, unreached population will get Family planning services, Private and Public health facilities will be expanding FP commodities and services, also changing the life style of couples and even recognition will made to Government from private sector.

Conclusion: There are lots of model for IPC activities whereas male engagement one of the models that we are thinking to implement. Some of the agencies already started it to implement HIV/AIDs through mobilize male in community level for effective utilization of condoms from outreach clinic. This model implemented for six months as piloting and will be continue after result from end line survey.

Family Planning Service Readiness in Karnali Province of Nepal

Deepak Paudel¹, Archana Amatya¹, Paras Chipalu¹,
Binamra Rajbhandari², Madhav Chaulagain²

¹Strengthening Systems for Better Health, Save the Children, Nepal,

²Strengthening Systems for Better Health, Abt Associates, Nepal

Abstract

Introduction: Family Planning (FP) service readiness refers to the ability and capacity of health facilities to offer a FP services, measured through selected tracer items that include trained staff, guidelines, equipment, diagnostic capacity and medicines and commodities. Objectives and Methods: The findings are extracted from the 2018 Health Facility Readiness Survey with objectives to measure service readiness and quality of care. Sample were drawn from 10 hospitals, 13 PHCCs, 81 HPs and 140 exit clients. Ethical clearance was obtained from NHRC and data analysis was carried out in Stata.

Findings: Almost all facilities offer three temporary (condom, pills and depo) FP services, 36% offer Long Acting Reversible Contraception (LARC i.e. implant and IUD) and 7% offer sterilization. Only 39% facilities had at least one staff trained on IUD, 52% on implants and 57% on counselling. Auditory privacy was maintained in 75% facilities, functional sterilization equipment available in 80% facilities. Only 37% facilities maintained at least one month's supply of IUD. FP counseling kit box was used in 63% facilities and medical eligibility criterial tool in 32% facilities, informed choice poster in 80% facilities. Overall FP service readiness was 67% for all facilities. Only 47% provider confirmed pregnancy status before offering services and 41% followed abhishadan counseling.

Conclusion: The survey showed concerns on availability of wide range of FP methods especially LARC and quality of services delivered by health facilities and identified areas of improvements. Improving in service availability including LARC and quality would result better uptake of FP services.

Disclaimer: The contents of this abstract are the sole responsibility of authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of USAID or the organization employing the authors.

Assessing knowledge, attitude and practices of family planning among women reproductive aged in four districts of Nepal

Deepika Bhatt¹, Raman Shrestha¹

¹Marie stopes Nepal/Sunaulo Parivar Nepal

Abstract

Background: Young, rural and poor women have the highest unmet need for Family Planning (FP) and struggle to access quality, comprehensive services due to limited health facilities with skilled staff and supplies. The objective of the study was to measure the current level of knowledge, attitude and practice of FP to guide program interventions.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 425 women of reproductive age (WRA) in four districts (Bajura, Tanahun, Sindhuli and Khotang). The sample size was determined using population proportionate sampling. A multi stage sampling techniques was used to identify households and respondents.

Findings: All respondents were aware about a method of FP and 53% of respondents were using either modern or traditional method. Majority of respondents (21%) were using injectables, followed by implant (17.3%). Majority of the respondent (79%) accessed FP services at government health facility. 99% of respondents felt FP should be planned and discussed between the partners and should wait at least 3 years before having another child. Women in the community still believed in Myth and misconceptions about FP such as unmarried women can't carry IUCD due to its load (60%), use of FP leads to infertility (49%) and IUCD leads to cancer (48%).

Conclusions: There is clear discrepancy between FP knowledge and practice in these districts. The study found many myths and misconceptions associated with various methods of FP. Interventions designed to improve FP uptake need to address these issues to increase acceptance of FP in these communities.

Acceptability and feasibility of the intervention on postpartum contraceptive utilization in rural Nepal

Aparna Tiwari¹, Sheela Maru², Hari Jung Rayamazi¹, Sita Saud¹,
Rita Bhatt¹, Wan-Ju Wu²

¹Nyaya Health Nepal, ²Possible Health, American Samoa

Abstract

Background: Unmet need for postpartum contraception is high in rural Nepal. Integrating contraceptive counseling with other reproductive health care can be more effective than stand-alone sessions. In collaboration with Nepal MOH, Nyaya Health Nepal's Community Health Worker (CHW) system delivers home-based integrated reproductive, maternal, newborn, and child health (RMNCH) intervention. Structured contraceptive counseling for postpartum women was integrated at home-based postnatal care.

Methodologies: We used Balanced Counseling Strategy (BCS) developed by the Population Council for contraceptive counseling. Originally used for post-abortion, we adapted BCS so CHWs can use in the home-setting for postpartum women. This intervention was first implemented in Kamalbazar, Achham in February 2017 and was later expanded to other areas in Achham and Dolakha. All postpartum women received the counseling at first, fifth and tenth postpartum months. We used qualitative methods to determine the acceptability and feasibility of this intervention in Kamalbazar. We conducted ten structured individual interviews: four women, three husbands present in the counseling and three care providers.

Results: Qualitative analysis shows that the intervention was well accepted as participants appreciated the counseling provided in homes. They believe CHW's counseling has helped improve knowledge on contraceptive methods than in the past. They perceive the intervention has helped increase modern methods use and decrease unwanted pregnancies. They also perceive using BCS cards as one of the effective elements in the counseling.

Conclusions: CHWs delivering structured contraceptive counseling integrated with RMNCH care in the community is well received, accepted and feasible in rural communities.

Method specific counselling in LARC Method of Family Planning

Jenis Chaudhary
ADRA Nepal

Abstract

Counseling is not only giving information but is an act of helping the client to see things more clearly, possibly from a different view point. This can enable the client to focus on feelings, experiences or behavior with a goal to facilitating positive change. Family planning counselling is the process of helping the clients and people from the village or specific community to make informed and voluntary choices about number of children they want to have and the spacing of children within their family or limiting the child. Privacy and confidentiality are the most important part of counselling. Counseling is done in different settings to single clients, couples and by group information sharing methods. Depending upon the situation, they have their own limitations and advantages.

Every step of counseling is important; however, method specific counseling has its unique role to retain the decision made by client, extract the fear from client, and to increase the ownership of chosen method. Method specific counselling is provided once a person has chosen a specific family planning method. For the demand generation in LARC Method most of the health workers use this method of counselling to the couple and clients who need the long gap between two children and who do not want to use permanent method as well as to the adolescent who wants to do something in a life and needs a gap for the children. Clients often lack knowledge about LARCs and frequently have misconceptions about them. LARC method may be perceived as newer and have historically been less used in population. In spite of these barriers, LARC methods are acceptable to many clients, especially when client centered and efficacy-based counseling is provided in an LARC service clinical setting that supports contraceptive choice and is free of coercion. Method specific counseling has helped to increase the acceptance of LARC among service users and also helped to increase its uptake among marginalized populations like Muslims.

Couple interaction program supports eligible couples to decide contraception uptake: evidence from a community experience at Majhkot, Pyuthan

Juna Saru Magar¹, Ashmin Hari Bhattaraj¹

¹ADRA Nepal

Abstract

Background: Contraceptive uptake among eligible couples remains uncommon in rural Pyuthan and the non-use contributes to large burden of unintended pregnancy. We implemented couple interaction program to increase clients' desire to use family planning service by facilitating male involvement in family planning issues through interaction among couples who use family planning service and those who do not use.

Methodology: We conducted the interaction program in the catchment area of Majhkot Health Post of Pyuthan Municipality in November 2018. 20 couples participated in the event, out of which 5 couples were currently using contraception while 15 couples were not. Interaction program held for 120 minutes was moderated by health facility in-charge of Majhkot Health Post and Visiting Service Provider from ADRA Nepal.

Results: The interaction program revolved around discussion about advantages and disadvantages of modern family planning methods, their side effects, myths and misconceptions that existed in the community. At the end of the event, out of 15 couples who were not currently using contraception, 93% (14) couples decided to uptake Long Acting Reversible Contraceptive (LARC) services and immediately received the service. Out of the 14 couples who received LARC service, 12 couples opted for implant and 2 couples chose IUCD.

Conclusion: Couple interaction program helps eligible couples to know about family planning methods from the existing users and decide on which methods of contraception best suits them. This intervention would likely be replicated most readily to advocate about family planning services and increase the uptake of LARC in rural communities.

Increase availability of FP services by expanding the range of contraceptive methods in Rolpa

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¹UNFPA Nepal, ²Rolpa Hospital Nepal,

³Marie Stopes International/Sunaulo Parivar Nepal

Abstract

Background: The contraceptive prevalence rate is stagnant in Nepal. Among married women (15–49 years), only 1% and 3% use IUCD and Implant respectively. Further, 24% of women have an unmet need for FP. In order to address this gap, MoHP has been implementing the Visiting Provider Approach for expanding the long-acting reversible contraception services.

Rolpa district is one of the remotest districts of Nepal having CPR 37 % (FY16) and has been impacted by the decade long internal conflict. UNFPA in partnership with MoHP expanded VP service approach in Rolpa to reach the unreached population.

Methodology: Through the mobilization of Visiting Service Providers, who are dedicated providers for LARC, UNFPA reached 46 out of the 51 Health facilities in the district. Additionally, VPs provided on-site coaching to 35 Health service providers to enhance their skills in providing LARC services. Government HMIS data and project data used to assess the effectiveness of the intervention.

Results: HMIS data from the district showed an increase in CPR by 3% from FY16 to FY18. Similarly, the new acceptor for LARC has increased from 411 in FY17 to 809 in FY18. On-site coaching support was provided to 25 LARC trained service providers.

Lesson learned and recommendation: The onsite coaching by VPs to health facility has enhanced the skills of government staff and increased access to the population at last mile. This intervention through VP has shown a substantial increase in uptake of LARC services and can be replicated or scale-up to reach the most marginalized and vulnerable communities.

Continuum of Care using “CONNECT App” for FP

Lhamo Yangchen Sherpa¹, Nirija Shrestha¹, Thomas How¹
¹PSI Nepal

Abstract

Connect App is a unique and powerful tool that supports in providing convenient, trusted, access to health information, links to health services and on-going support for care across the continuum using mobile technology. The technological innovation has supported to bring quality health care closer to clients. Individual Client feedback can be collected directly into the system. The approach has not only reduced data entry errors but also provided real time data on client contributing to larger referral and demand for FP services.

Awareness, Attitude and Practice on contraception among the clients attending abortion Services at Seti Zonal Hospital

Mithu Saud
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Abstract

Background: Unwanted pregnancy may lead to unsafe abortion which can be prevented through the utilization of contraception. Contraceptive methods are the most important components to reduce unwanted pregnancies, maternal and child morbidity as well as mortality. There are several effective methods of contraception available to prevent unplanned pregnancy. The objective of this study was to identify awareness, attitude and practice on contraception among clients attending abortion services at Seti Zonal Hospital.

Methodologies: Cross-sectional research study included 94 women by using total enumeration sampling techniques from Safe abortion Unit of Seti zonal Hospital, during 12th August to 7th September 2018. Data were collected using structured face- to- face interview schedule. SPSS 16.0 software was used for data analysis. The statistical test chi square and pearson’s correlation was used.

Results: Majority of the respondents 59 (73.8%) had adequate awareness. Majority of the respondents (83%) had positive attitude in regard to use of contraception rather than termination of pregnancy. 44 respondents (46.8%) had inadequate practice and only 19 respondents (20.2%) had adequate practice towards contraception. There was significant association between types of family and level of awareness (P <.001). There was no correlation between awareness, attitude and practice.

Lesson learned: Acceptance of counseling service and intention to use family planning methods was high in the study participants. The results of study showed practice of acceptance of contraception was reducing among the clients. There is need to provide complete information to change their attitude towards contraception to increase its use in future.

Nari Paila Mobile Games: Developing and monitoring mobile games using social media and analytics

Naramaya Subba Limbu¹, Trishna Shah², Nokafu K. Sandra Chipanta¹, Christina Riley¹, Sarah Thompson¹, Shwetha Srinivasan¹, Khem Narayan Pokhrel¹, Dominick Shattuck¹
¹Institute for Reproductive Health, Georgetown University, ²Max L'agence Nepal

Abstract

Background: Structured properly, mobile app games have the potential to catalyze new conversations about reproductive health and menstruation, and challenge longstanding taboos and norms. “Nari Paila” (Women Journey), takes users through reproductive health decision points as they are encountered through a multi-generational family. Users are exposed to clear communication and positive norms about sensitive topics such as the menstrual cycle, menstrual hygiene management, family planning, and sex determination. The games integrate storytelling through wise goat Bakhri, who relates facts about each topic, while fighting off the challenges of the Yeti, who regularly interjects myths to thwart players’ success.

Methods: This presentation will briefly describe the games, but focus on the marketing approach and data collection opportunities of mobile games. Our Digital Media approach aims to harness the power of several channels that include Facebook, Instagram, Google Ads, TikTok, YouTube, and online news portals. The presentation will describe key advertisements and methods used for tracking outputs that include: online impressions, click through rates, user comments, and downloads.

Results: Nari Paila will be launched for free download on the Google Playstore in March of 2019. We will describe initial figures that reflect the initial reach of the games and the feedback we have received to this point.

Lessons: Girls and boys often enter puberty with little information about their changing bodies, fertility, or positive reproductive health behaviors. Nari Paila provides a new approach to build reproductive health knowledge, challenge harmful social norms, and strengthen adolescents’ reproductive health decision making as they approach adulthood in a fun and engaging way.

Demand generation and Service Linkage: Family Planning Camp promotion

Pranab Rajbhandari¹, Sunil Raj Sharma², Kundan Raj Acharya

¹Breakthrough Action Project/Johns Hopkins Center for Communication Programs,

²NHEICC Nepal

Abstract

Background: Family Planning service camps are planned and held each year across Nepal with the intention of reaching the unreached and providing needed FP services. There is some promotion of these camps but a strategic promotion is not conducted. Strategically well-promoted FP camps should increase the demand for services. Methods: The HC3 project supported the strategic promotion of FP camps implemented by the SIFPO project. These promotions were done through word of mouth through the existing outreach networks on the ground, through local FM radios, through street level announcements/miking and with pamphlets and posters.

Results: The promoted camps drew more people for services than un-promoted or not properly promoted camps. Lessons learnt: Service provision with demand generation, health promotion is more effective as those needing services will be properly informed and avail of the existing services. Strategic planned promotion of FP camps should be a necessary and important part of FP camp services to increase the uptake of services.

Local solutions: Tripartite discussions and solutions for improving access and service quality of Family Planning Services

Pranab Rajbhandari¹, Thaneswor Koirala¹

¹Breakthrough Action Project/Johns Hopkins Center for Communication Programs

Abstract

Background: Health promotion/demand generation and quality family planning service provision go hand in hand. When there is proper health promotion and demand is generated but the needed services are not available due to any existing constraints then that in turn reduces demand as the service seekers are unable to access needed services. Service sites across Nepal have been dependent on central level support and a number of service sites are not fully functional due to service constraints due to unavailability of resources to procure needed equipment. **Methods:** A local solution seeking method was implemented by meeting and discussing separately with the HFOMC committee, health facility staff and community members/service users about the availability and quality of locally available family planning services. These three groups were facilitated to jointly discuss the noted issues listing the positives and challenges.

Results: These local joint discussions helped to identify, clarify issues as well as possible local solutions. The local community health stakeholders were able to mobilize resources locally or seek resources to improve the quality and access of FP services. Some examples are of starting long-acting family planning services, establishing a proper counseling room, allocation of resources by the municipality for FP services, starting lab services, managing running water.

Lessons learnt: Local solutions are available and effective. Local coordination and discussions amongst stakeholders can provide solutions to improve access and quality of family planning services.

Is there discordance between Nepali family planning practitioner's knowledge and views of eligibility for contraception and criteria set out in the WHO Medical Eligibility Criteria (WHO MEC) guidelines?

Rajendra Gurung¹, Maureen Dariang²
¹NHSSP Nepal, ²NHSSP Myanmar

Abstract

Family planning modern method use among currently married women in Nepal has over the years have stagnated while unmet need for family planning is still high. Contraceptive method mix is skewed to permanent methods, uptake of long acting reversible contraceptives is low and method use among adolescents and youths are sub-optimum.

There are evidences that family planning service provider's professional lacking of appropriate knowledge, skills and harboring of misperceptions about family planning limits the access and use of contraceptives by women and couple putting them in risk of unintended pregnancies and its consequences. Family planning service provider's adherence to eligibility criteria, providers own attitude, perception, and management of side effects may not comply with the current evidence based global standards practice and norms.

A family planning knowledge and attitude of 65 Obstetrics/Gynecologist and 111 non-specialist family planning providers was assessed using 10 knowledge and 10 attitude questionnaires. Widespread knowledge gaps and misperceptions on family planning was found with all service providers. Some of the knowledge and perception responses of providers do not comply with the current global standard and norm. Except in one knowledge question, no statistical significant difference (Z value, P value) was noted among the responses of two categories of providers.

Knowledge updates on family planning of family planning providers at different level through multiple approaches is heralded to reduce these family planning related medical barriers.

Visiting Providers (VP) in Nepal increase access to family planning services in remote areas – Experiences from a post-earthquake context

Rajendra Gurung¹, Yubaraj Paudel², Maureen Dariang³
¹NHSSP Nepal, ²Former NHSSP Nepal, ³NHSSP Myanmar

Abstract

Nepal's 2015 earthquake put significant pressure on an already fragile public health system. Family Planning (FP) services were badly affected, particularly in hard-to-reach/affected areas and in temporary settlements. Although 69% of the birthing centres in five of the affected districts (Sindhuli, Okhaldhunga, Lalitpur, Nuwakot, Gorkha), had at least one skilled provider trained in intrauterine contraceptive device (IUCD) insertion, and 46% had at least one provider trained on implant insertions, only 20% and 33% of them provided IUCD and implant services respectively. A shortage of trained IUCD and implant providers combined with the lack of confidence of trained providers to provide IUCD/implant services, and non-availability of IUCD/implant insertion and removal kit contributed to the low uptake.

A multipronged approach including visiting providers contributed to continued contraceptive uptake by women who had limited access to health services. The post-earthquake FP support programme implemented from February to July 2016, primarily aimed at expanding long acting reversible contraceptives (LARC) services tailored to the needs of earthquake affected districts. Furthermore, the intervention package also addressed pre-existing service delivery challenges that had been aggravated during and after the earthquake, based on the principle of Building Back Better.

Recent trend of HIV/AIDS demands FP to reach the unreached

Ramesh Kumar Yadav
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Abstract

The broad range of programs and several million dollars' being invested in prevention of HIV positive is very low which is only prevented by condom use, despite occupying equal proportion of death and living among people under age of 15 in Nepal where HIV+ incidences is higher among youths.

The paper is descriptive review of secondary available reports by different organizations. My findings show many teenagers had first sex at the age of 11, eventually sex with multiple partner and steep decrease in use of condom by teenagers and males. As a result, in overall, trending shift of HIV/AIDS from high risk population to low risk population, which is also again higher in males. The HIV/AIDS incidences became low among high risk and targeted group but the number has been increased among low risk population.

Since HIV positive is widely spread through sexual contact in the context of Nepal. By reviewing secondary data, most of the programs in Nepal are targeted to girls than boys. It has been an evident to suggest to increase the sexuality education and condom use by strategic reforms for Behavior Change Communication targeting male partners too. This would broadly and inherently decrease the AIDS incidences, early pregnancy, illegal abortion issues and birth rate.

It has been eminent to reach low risk population equally than only targeting the high risk groups. Condom use is the most effective, easily available and accessible means of Family planning method to prevent a large number of FP related issues.

Policy to Enabling Environment of Long acting reversible contraceptive (LARC) at Kamal Rural Municipality, Jhapa

Ramchandra Mishra
Kamal Rural Municipality

Abstract

Global efforts to prevent unintended pregnancies and improve pregnancy spacing among adolescents and youth will reduce maternal and infant morbidity and mortality, decrease rates of unsafe abortion, decrease HIV/STI incidence, improve nutritional status, keep girls in school, improve economic opportunities, and contribute toward reaching the Sustainable Development Goals¹.

LARC is seen as unsafe or ill-suited for adolescents and youth by many providers who share medically inaccurate information influenced by their own biases and beliefs. But the truth of the matter is that LARC is one of the safest, most convenient and most effective contraceptive technologies for youth. These methods offer gold standard contraceptive protection and require little to no maintenance - a feature that adolescents and youth can appreciate. Adolescents and youth are diverse and come from a myriad of societal, religious, and cultural contexts but what we have in common is our need for privacy and respect in the area of sexual and reproductive health. We rely on health care providers, donors, policy makers, and governments to trust our decisions and our call for highly effective contraceptive options rather than question our knowledge and understanding of our own bodies and needs².

Current attention to increasing access to family planning has increased focus on ensuring that policy, programming and practice are "evidence-based." Policymaking, program design, and implementation are complex processes, and understanding how research evidence informs decision-making related to the three is difficult to measure. Adding to the complexity is that researchers and decision-makers define evidence differently, with researchers taking a more narrow view of evidence as findings from research studies while decision-makers include a wider range of information, in addition to research, as evidence, such as M&E, government reports and policy documents, community views and complaints, and professional experience. Furthermore, not only does the literature show that decision-makers and researchers have little understanding of, and appreciation for, each other's work environments, neither group have professional incentives to ensure that decisions are evidence-based. Building cultures of evidence that bring decision-makers and researchers together could help increase use of evidence by decision-makers and improve the utility of the evidence produced by researchers. Views of what evidence is need to be more aligned with researchers' understanding that "evidence-based" does not only mean "research evidence-based" to decision-makers and with decision-makers understanding the value of robust research evidence among other evidence they consider when making decisions³.

Kamal RM is situated in the north-western part of Jhapa district also known as semi urban village. The population is 52485, MWRA are 10638, excepted live birth is 1048 and the area of RM is 79.78 KM². There are 2 health posts, 1 rural health units, 11 EPI clinics, 6 PHC-ORCs and 24 FCHVs which are working in service provision.

Family planning is not separate, but an important integral part of other health programmes. so we make planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation processes of all health programmes, including family planning, are very similar and integrated in our rural municipality. It is now well recognized that expanding access to contraceptive services and improving health outcomes require services to be delivered in ways that respect, protect and fulfil the human rights of everyone who seeks, or uses contraceptive information and services.

LARC is started in Health set up of Kamal RM since FY 2071/072. Although there were regular and quality services, availability of trained human resources in regular basis, a few numbers of clients were attracted toward LARC on starting year.

The local Government of kamal RM makes a policy to provide incentive for client as well as service providers to develop attraction toward ANC visit, Institutional Delivery, PNC visit IMMUNIZATION and LARC Method since FY 2074/075 as a key program of women Health and Empowerment. FCHV incentive program, mother group promotion program and orientation to mother group through health workers are included as supportive programme also. As the impact of such policy, the numbers of New acceptor of IUDs were 27 and IMPLANT were 52 in FY 2074/075. Now a days, the total number of LARC users are 111 including 39 IUD and 72 IMPLANT. All clients of LARC are satisfied with the services.

Although, Incentive is a very strong short-termed way to attract target population but it is not a proper solution. Regular quality service, problem management and counseling with trained human resources, FCHV mobilization, healthy mother group education and orientation increases the clients of LARC and help to increase contraceptive prevalence rate, decrease TFR and unwanted abortion, empowered the mother to control her fertility, eventually increase the power of decision making of woman.

References

1. GLOBAL CONSENSUS STATEMENT FOR EXPANDING CONTRACEPTIVE CHOICE FOR ADOLESCENTS AND YOUTH TO INCLUDE LONG-ACTING REVERSIBLE CONTRACEPTION, International Youth Alliance for Family Planning.
2. International Youth Alliance for Family Planning
3. Hardee, Karen, Kelsey Wright, and Joanne Spicehandler. 2015. "Family Planning Policy, Program, and Practice Decision-making: The Role of Research Evidence and Other Factors," Working Paper. Washington, DC: Population Council, The Evidence Project

Bringing services to the Doorsteps

Sapana Joshi
ADRA Nepal

Abstract

We decided to go in Timurchaur Village, it would then be easier to understand the reason behind not to use family planning as a whole in Timurchaur village of Jhimruk Rural Municipality. When I arrived in Tusara, with the help of Tusara Health Facility staffs, we travelled in Timurchaur for the Out-Reach Clinic. It took 3 hours to reach the clinic. On the 20th (Nepali date) of every month, health facility staff have had been going to the outreach clinic at Timurchaur. I also started going since February 3rd, 2019. That place is far away from any other health facility, it's very difficult for them which means if they need medicine for anything like for instance; Paracetamol, they will have to wait for 20th of every month. There're more of a Dalit Caste in that area. Poverty, Ignorance, illiteracy is much there.

Every month health facility staff go to the village to conduct Out Reach Clinic at that time staffs also teach them about the family planning methods but no anyone show interest in this matter. If Women have Unwanted Pregnancy then, they are ready to terminate the baby not at all interested in going in use family planning methods. By the Co-ordination with health facility staff, local elected chairperson of that ward and , visiting service providers of ADRA Nepal gave education on family planning .VSP of ADRA Nepal told them, range of modern family planning methods including Condoms, the pills, Depo and Long acting reversible contraceptive and permanent methods. We not only told them about family planning methods but also gave education about consequences of not using family planning methods like complications related to abortion, degradation of women health by giving birth to many child, pregnancy related issue, sexual and reproductive health, recurrent child birth can lead to serious health complications and maternal or child mortality and morbidity and avoid misconceptions around contraceptive side effects.

We interact with them, the most serious drawback of the women not using family planning methods is because of their husband's foul thought towards Contraceptive use because they still don't support the idea. Husbands reject the contraceptive method. Not only wives at homes threatened but also female community health volunteer (FCHCVs). Men accuse the health care workers of ruining their family. Even, if female wants to use the contraceptive methods makes reject it .Since their husbands are going to India for the source of income, they come home every 314 times a year but still they disapproved to use long term reversible contraceptive neither short acting.

Because of too many abortion, because of giving birth too many babies, their health has been really bad but still their husband's don't care. The ability to plan one's family and time and space pregnancies is a basic human right. We told them family planning is not only a matter of human right, it's also a central to women's empowerment. Gender inequality and discrimination against Girls, Women mean they are often robbed of the right to make their own life decisions. And women have the right to make these informed choice. We told them family planning is committed to promoting change across society but it only when there's equality between gender while using family planning services the programme will achieve success and the women achieve the highest level of health.

Respected elected chairperson of this ward show his massive effort to increased attention towards family planning in that programme .He gave his good voice there, it's your body, if you want to not get pregnant and delay your pregnancy I am supportive and it's totally every women right and every women choice and it's not up to someone else and he told the women of reproductive age group that if their husband's threatened them, punished them because of they use family planning methods then chairperson take strict action towards them.

The issue of family planning has been an enormous challenge for marginalized women's besides this all these abstracts we are succeed to provide family planning methods ;Long acting reversible contraceptive -Implant to our 3 clients there. It's our remarkable achievement in that Dalit Community where people never use family planning methods before. I really enjoy working as a VSP and thank you ADRA Nepal for giving me this opportunity which help me to learn many thing directly from grassroots level and increase my self-confidence of working. And ADRA Nepal is very thankful towards such a great social leader who speak for women rights and also thankful to tusara health facility. Because of that I got a phone call from there to come to the village in next Outreach clinic because there are more woman who wants to do the use of family planning methods, said a health facility staff. And our little efforts give us beautiful fruitful results and this is our great success story.

Community Games for Family Planning – Men and youth need to play these games too!

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Abstract

Background: Studies have identified inequitable access to reproductive health (RH) services for many communities in Nepal, especially among hard-to-reach (HTR) communities. The Fertility Awareness for Community Transformation project implemented Pragati, a series of nine games, in five districts in Nepal. Games targeted 15–25 year olds in HTR communities and covered social and gender norms associated with family planning (FP), fertility awareness (FA), and knowledge of FP, particularly around side effects and misconceptions.

Methodology: Pragati games were implemented from January, 2017 to March, 2018. The games were evaluated using a mixed-methods quasi-experimental study design to a sample of 3,645 systematically selected men and women 18 – 39 years old across all districts. Focus group discussions contextualized women’s experiences.

Results: The games were played 9,315 times, with 118,123 of contacts, 66% of contacts were identified as HTR in their district. Men/Women who played at least four games were 7.4 times more likely to have a high FA score. Individuals with a high FA score were 1.7 times more likely to be using an FP method. Individuals with a high acceptance of FP score were 2.1 times more likely to be using a FP method and 3.6 times more likely to use an FP method in the next six months.

Lessons Learned: Pragati games offer an easy and comfortable platform to address FP and RH in the community. The use of games may be particularly relevant in countries like Nepal where discussion of RH and FP may be taboo, particularly in mixed-sex contexts.

Family planning in Nepal: Facility Readiness, Provider Behaviour, and Client Satisfaction

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Abstract

Background: Nepal has made notable progress in the use of contraceptives and reducing fertility after the 1994 ICDP. However, the CPR has become stagnant at around 43%, unmet need decreased slightly to 24% and demand satisfied constant at 56% over the last decade. Limited access to quality family planning services is considered as key factors contributing to client's reluctance to uptake and continue contraceptive methods.

Objective: This analysis examines the factors associated with facility readiness, provider behaviour and client satisfaction with the help of a framework adopted from WHO and Donabedian to examine service availability and readiness assessment.

Methodology: Assessment was based on 869 facilities and 772 exit clients administered in NHFS 2015. Cross-tabulation and multivariate regression were used for analysis.

Results: Results indicated that about half of the facilities had high level of overall readiness score. The readiness varied across the provinces. The client satisfaction score was in high category in about half of the family planning client (49%). Highest percentage (73%) of the clients in Province-4 had the overall client satisfaction score in high category. This percentage was lowest in Karnali (35%) and Province-7 (37%). Client satisfaction was dependent on the waiting time, caste/ethnicity and age of the clients. The health worker behaviour was found to be one of the major contributors to client dissatisfaction.

Lessons Learned and Recommendation: It is suggested to develop, implement and monitor a standard service protocol for each level of public health institution. A series of technical discussions in re-thinking private sector engagement in FP services would help in addressing some of these challenges.

Awareness and use of Emergency Contraception in Hill and Mountain areas of Nepal

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¹SHOPS Plus, Abt Associates Nepal, ²SHOPS Plus, Abt Associates United States

Abstract

In rural Nepal, the modern contraceptive prevalence rate is 41%, and the unmet need for family planning is 25% (NDHS, 2016). The Sustaining Health Outcomes through the Private Sector Plus (SHOPS Plus) project supports the Nepal CRS Company (CRS), a social marketing organization, to increase modern contraception access and use in rural, underserved communities. To catalyze reductions in unmet need, CRS's Ghar Ghar Maa Swasthya (GGMS) project in rural Nepal generates family planning demand through behavior change communication and increases contraceptive access through social marketing.

We conducted a household survey in 49 primarily rural districts of Nepal. The survey sampled 3,293 women aged 15-49. The survey used a multi-stage cluster design stratified by hill and mountain areas. Data collection was conducted from December to February, 2018. Data analysis used descriptive statistics to examine determinants related to family planning uptake and use. This abstract on emergency contraception (EC) is the part of larger survey.

A total of 22% of women have heard of EC. Women who are more highly educated, unmarried, younger, and urban are more likely to have heard of EC. Among women who have heard about EC, only 6% of women have ever used EC. Women who have ever used EC are mostly from hill districts (89%), urban (78%), wealthy (58% in top two wealth quintiles), and highly educated (62% have an SLC or higher).

Knowledge regarding the purpose of EC could be improved: less than two-thirds of women reported that EC is an emergency pregnancy prevention measure to be used up to three days after unprotected sex. The majority of women (83%) reported that EC can be purchased from a pharmacy. About one-third also reported that EC could be purchased from a private hospital or clinic.

The program should target rural, less educated women to close the gap in low EC awareness and knowledge about what the product is and from where it can be purchased so that women have full information about this effective family planning method. Given the high rates of traditional contraception (withdrawal) and irregular use of other methods due to migration, it is important for women to be able to access EC as a backup method.

Evidence based Smart Family Planning National campaign – Paradigm shift in reaching audiences

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Abstract

Background: Family Planning has been implemented in Nepal for more than 50 years but demand was seen to be stagnant. FP stakeholders saw the need to conduct a national FP campaign to increase the visibility and use of FP.

Methods: An aspirational family planning campaign branded as Smart planning for your life was designed based on evidence. Existing data was analyzed to tease out the unreached by Family Planning. The unreached according to the national data were those 15-26 of age, young couples with 0 or 1 parity and mothers immediately post-partum. The data depicted good family planning practice during cohabitation and migrants, a major group in Nepal, presented a picture of low need during separation.

The national FP campaign provided saturation coverage identifiable by a brand and mnemonic (Pariwar Niyajan Smart Bancha Jeewan) through mass media, below the line events (melas) with popular artists, further reach multiplication through social media, street level coverage through tuk tuks, cinema halls, as well as one on one outreach through EPI/FP promotion integration, household visits, peer facilitation deep into selected locations in catchment areas across the country.

Results: The FP campaign was monitored through omnibus surveys for reach, and through data collection and analysis for one on one reach. The yearly surveys depicted high reach across the country while the DHS 2016 also presented the strong reach of the campaign across the country. The national campaign was referred to by the intended audience in catchment areas.

Lessons learnt: An evidence-based targeted national campaign using a multi-mix method designed with consultation of the intended audience, implemented at scale nationally and locally, monitored for reach, is effective in creating awareness and generating demand for FP services.

Utilization of contraceptives and associated factors among eligible couples of Santhal community

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Abstract

Family planning is defined as "A way of thinking and living that is adopted voluntarily, upon the basis of knowledge, attitudes and responsible decision by individuals and couples, in order to promote the health and welfare of the family group and thus contribute effectively to the social development of a country". The research entitled, "Utilization of contraceptives and associated factors among eligible couples of Santhal community of Jhapa district", was a community based cross sectional study whose main objective was to assess the prevalence and factors affecting the use of contraceptives among eligible couples of Santhal community of Jhapa Gaunpalika.

The descriptive cross sectional study was carried out in Jhapa Gaunpalika of Jhapa district by identifying clusters of Santhal community and 200 respondents were study population by census method. The data collection technique was face to face interview and the tool used was semi structured questionnaire. The collected data was coded, decoded and cleaned and then was entered into SPSS version 16.00 and analysis was done by using simple descriptive statistics like percentage, frequency etc. Chi-Square test and Fishers' Exact Test were applied for establishing the association between the variables at 5% level of significance.

The CPR of the Santhal community was found to be 41.5%. Out of 200 respondents, 128 were female and 72 were male and majority of them were of the age group 30 and above. Most of them were followers of Hindu religion and were engaged in daily wages for earning. They had low educational status and most of them were married at the age of 18 or below, around 58% of them had 2 or more than two children. The association was seen between sex of the respondent and utilization of contraceptives. Similarly, age at marriage, educational status, number of children and type of family were found to be associated with the use of contraceptives among the eligible couples of those clusters. The study showed the utilization of permanent methods by females for the purpose of birth control which was influenced or motivated by the government provision of incentives for permanent sterilization. Male members were found to be rarely involved in utilization of contraceptives and were found to be unaware or inactive in FP related matters. Also, couples had less knowledge on contraceptives and spacing devices.

Increasing LARC uptake in Rupandehi district through targeted demand generation interventions

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Abstract

Background: Nepal has committed to increase health seeking behavior of populations with high unmet need for modern contraception to improve the stagnated mCPR of 43% since 2011 (FP2020 Commitment). Through ADRA Nepal's Family Planning Service Strengthening Program (FPSSP), we mobilized 5 Visiting Service Providers (VSPs) to increase demand for and provide LARC service in communities of Rupandehi district. This paper presents the findings of various demand generation activities carried out to increase the uptake of FP methods through VSP mobilization in Rupandehi district.

Methodology: VSPs implemented community and facility-based demand interventions focusing mainly on counselling, sensitization and education activities to promote wider discussion of family planning among target groups from August 2018 to January 2019 in Rupandehi district. 346 males and 615 females including adolescents were reached through FP awareness sessions, 62 couples through couple interaction program, and 60 MDAG people through FP discussion.

Findings: These demand generation interventions have increased health seeking behavior of women to receive family planning service in Rupandehi district. Out of 1438 women who received LARC service from the district in the intervention period, 866 (60%) were provided by VSPs mobilized in 36 health facilities where there was no institutionalized LARC service. Out of 1028 clients reached by VSPs for balanced counseling, 866 (84%) clients received the service. Significant proportion (90%) of the service recipients were from disadvantaged groups like Dalit, janajati, Madhesi and Muslim. Number of females receiving LARC service each month in the district have significantly risen from 54 in August 2018 to 276 in January 2019.

Conclusion: Targeted demand generation activities can make an important contribution to increasing LARC uptake. These activities can be adopted at community and facility level targeting key populations with high unmet need to increase mCPR of the country.

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